

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials

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MAIN AUTHORS	
Name	Organisation
Eirini Efthymiadou, Andromachi Kalaouzi, Elena Nistikaki	Q-PLAN
Marta Redrado, Pilar Pérez, Eva Sanchis	AITIIP

QUALITY REVIEWERS	
Name	Organisation
Marta Redrado	AITIIP

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. INTRODUCTION	7
1.1 Scope of the Deliverable	7
1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables.....	8
1.3 Structure of the Deliverable.....	8
2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	10
2.1 Overview and Objectives	10
2.2 Target Audiences, Key Messages and Key Results.....	11
2.2.1 <i>The VIBES Target Audiences</i>	11
2.2.2 <i>The VIBES Stakeholders Board</i>	12
2.2.3 <i>Synergies with Other Projects and Initiatives</i>	15
2.2.4 <i>The VIBES Key Messages</i>	17
2.2.5 <i>The VIBES Key Exploitable Results</i>	19
2.3 Role and Responsibilities	20
2.4 The Gender Dimension	21
3. COMMUNICATION MEANS AND CHANNELS	21
3.1 Visual Identity and Promotional Package	21
3.1.1 <i>Logo</i>	21
3.1.2 <i>Leaflets</i>	23
3.1.3 <i>Infographic</i>	26
3.1.4 <i>Promotional Videos</i>	28
3.1.5 <i>Document and Presentation Templates</i>	31
3.1.6 <i>Image Galleries</i>	31
3.2 VIBES Website	33
3.3 Social Media Accounts	36
3.4 E-Newsletters	37
3.5 Press Kit.....	38
3.5.1 <i>Press Releases and Articles</i>	38
3.5.2 <i>Digital Media Channels</i>	38
3.6 Articles in Press and Industry Magazines.....	40

3.7	Participation in Events/ Fairs/ Info-days	43
3.8	Layman’s Report	48
3.9	Internal Communication	48
4.	DISSEMINATION MEANS AND CHANNELS	49
4.1	Scientific Publications	49
4.2	Participation in Scientific Conferences	50
4.3	Organisation of Events	56
4.3.1	<i>COMPOSIFORUM International Events</i>	<i>56</i>
4.3.2	<i>Demonstration and other Workshops</i>	<i>57</i>
4.3.3	<i>Roundtables</i>	<i>60</i>
4.3.4	<i>Final Conference</i>	<i>62</i>
5.	TRAINING PROGRAMME.....	64
5.1	Training strategy	64
5.2	Objectives, Target Audiences and Themes	66
5.3	Training Methodology.....	67
5.3.1	<i>Face to face training sessions.....</i>	<i>67</i>
5.3.2	<i>Online training sessions.....</i>	<i>67</i>
5.3.3	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>68</i>
5.4	Training activities	68
5.4.1	<i>Research Workshops for researchers and technicians</i>	<i>68</i>
5.4.2	<i>Summer Training Course</i>	<i>70</i>
5.4.3	<i>E-learning</i>	<i>76</i>
5.4.4	<i>Training for Industrial Professionals.....</i>	<i>78</i>
5.5	Training activities calendar	81
6.	TIME FRAME OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES.....	83
7.	PERFORMANCE INDICATORS, MONITORING AND REPORTING	85
7.1	Performance Indicators and Monitoring	85
7.2	Reporting.....	91
7.2.1	<i>Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template.....</i>	<i>92</i>
7.2.2	<i>News Reporting Template.....</i>	<i>92</i>
7.2.3	<i>Event Reporting Form.....</i>	<i>93</i>
7.2.4	<i>External Conferences and Events Template</i>	<i>93</i>
8.	CONCLUSIONS	94

ANNEX 1. CONTACT LIST OF VIBES STAKEHOLDERS	95
ANNEX 2. DECLARATION OF ACCEPTANCE AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM.....	96
ANNEX 3. STAKEHOLDERS BOARD TERMS OF REFERENCE	99
ANNEX 4. DOCUMENT AND PRESENTATION TEMPLATES	102
ANNEX 5. VIBES PRESENCE ON SOCIAL MEDIA	105
VIBES Page on Twitter/X.....	105
VIBES Page and Metrics on LinkedIn	106
VIBES Page and Metrics on Facebook	110
VIBES Page on YouTube	111
ANNEX 6. VIBES SEVENTH NEWSLETTER	112
ANNEX 7. VIBES EIGHTH NEWSLETTER AND FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE	118
ANNEX 8. VIBES EIGHTH PRESS RELEASE	128
ANNEX 9. VIBES NINTH PRESS RELEASE	130
ANNEX 10. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION REPORTING TEMPLATE	133
ANNEX 11. NEWS REPORTING TEMPLATE.....	134
ANNEX 12. EVENT REPORTING FORM	135
ANNEX 13. EXTERNAL CONFERENCES AND EVENTS TEMPLATE.....	137

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per stakeholder type</i>	14
<i>Figure 2. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per country</i>	14
<i>Figure 3. Gender of VIBES Stakeholders Board members</i>	14
<i>Figure 4. VIBES logo with tag line</i>	22
<i>Figure 5. VIBES logo without tag line</i>	22
<i>Figure 6. The color codes of VIBES logo</i>	22
<i>Figure 7. The combined logo of Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking, Bio-based Industries Consortium and Horizon2020</i>	23
<i>Figure 8. The first leaflet of VIBES</i>	24
<i>Figure 9. The second leaflet of VIBES</i>	25
<i>Figure 10. The infographic of VIBES in a poster form</i>	26
<i>Figure 11. The infographic of VIBES in a roll up form</i>	27
<i>Figure 12. The story board of the VIBES first promotional video</i>	28
<i>Figure 13. VIBES team members present their role and achievements</i>	31
<i>Figure 14. Images of VIBES News</i>	32
<i>Figure 15. Google analytics presenting the users (visitors) of the website</i>	35
<i>Figure 16. Alejandro Ibrahim (PLATA) I-Talks</i>	39
<i>Figure 17. AITIIP at LOOPS webinar</i>	39
<i>Figure 18. Demonstration workshop in Teruel</i>	57
<i>Figure 19. Demonstration workshop in Zaragoza</i>	58
<i>Figure 20. Demonstration workshop in Barcelona</i>	58
<i>Figure 21. Additional demonstration workshop at PLATA facilities in Teruel</i>	59
<i>Figure 22. Workshop for primary school students in AITIIP</i>	60
<i>Figure 23. VIBES first roundtable in Montpellier</i>	61
<i>Figure 24. VIBES second roundtable in Zaragoza</i>	62
<i>Figure 25. VIBES final conference in Barcelona</i>	63
<i>Figure 26. Workshop about Circular Economy at AITIIP</i>	69
<i>Figure 27. Workshop at University of Limerick</i>	69
<i>Figure 28. Workshop at University of Zaragoza</i>	70
<i>Figure 29. 1st Technological breakfast</i>	79
<i>Figure 30. Workshop in PLATA</i>	79
<i>Figure 31. 2nd Technological Breakfast</i>	80

List of Tables

<i>Table 1. VIBES stakeholder groups and sub-groups.....</i>	<i>11</i>
<i>Table 2. Projects/ initiatives related to VIBES.....</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Table 3. Key messages and means used for VIBES targeted stakeholder groups</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>Table 4. VIBES key exploitable results and outcomes</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Table 5. VIBES social media accounts</i>	<i>36</i>
<i>Table 6. Articles about VIBES in local press and industry magazines</i>	<i>40</i>
<i>Table 7. Presentation of VIBES at relevant events</i>	<i>43</i>
<i>Table 8. Internal mailing lists.....</i>	<i>48</i>
<i>Table 9. Presentation of VIBES approach at scientific conferences & events</i>	<i>51</i>
<i>Table 10. KPIs and target values.....</i>	<i>85</i>
<i>Table 11. Reporting tools for monitoring communication and dissemination activities</i>	<i>91</i>

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the third and final updated version of the “Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report” of the VIBES project, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. The main objective of VIBES is to develop and demonstrate a new, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

With reference to the initial report and the first and second update elaborated in D6.2., D6.3. and D6.4. respectively, this document describes the overall communication and dissemination strategy, the means and channels for communication and dissemination, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and the partners’ responsibilities in this respect. It includes specific communication, dissemination and training activities that have been carried out by the VIBES consortium members, in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results.

The report outlines:

- **Why and what to disseminate:** the rationale of the project communication and dissemination strategy as well as the basic project-related information that has been conveyed throughout the project are presented in Chapter 2.
- **To whom:** the key stakeholder groups that serve as the main audiences for the project’s communication and dissemination campaign are also presented in Chapter 2.
- **By what means:** all the means and channels that have been used by the project partners to successfully implement the communication, dissemination and training activities, are included in Chapters 3, 4 and 5 respectively.
- **When:** a time frame ensuring that the timing of the communication, dissemination and training activities has been appropriate during the lifespan of the project, is provided in Chapter 6.
- **Monitoring of the process:** the indicators to measure success on the communication, dissemination and training actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project, have been updated and they are specified in Chapter 7.

1. Introduction

VIBES aims to be a success story of collaboration among science, innovation and industrial entities from different European countries to minimise any negative impacts on the environment due to industrial activities and therefore improve European Citizens' wellbeing. For this reason, communicating this story is of paramount importance to maximize project results and multiply their impact at European level.

The main aim of VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Plan is to provide the communication, dissemination and training strategy of the project. It has been updated and will be implemented during and after the project. Effective communication, dissemination and training activities have been carried out, following a good communication and dissemination strategy that guarantees to:

- Address audiences beyond the action's own community (including the media and the public).
- Clearly define objectives
- Achieve the highest possible impact by involving creative and expert people.

The current communication, dissemination and training report is the third and final updated version of the initial plan, assisting partners in designing and implementing their publicity, communication and engagement activities, within the framework of the project. It includes guidelines that have helped achieve maximum visibility, to pave the way for a successful market uptake of the VIBES results. The initial report and its guidelines have been subjected to modifications and updates in line with the project progress and the experience that has been gained through the various project activities. As such, the communication, awareness raising and dissemination strategy that is presented in this report has not been static. It is a living document that has been continuously reviewed in specific time intervals to account for any challenge or opportunity that may have arisen during the project.

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The objective of the Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities report is to target different audiences to create a European Identity, strengthening European Industry and building European Bridges. The main goals are:

1. To raise European citizens' awareness about cooperative research & innovation projects as the way to meet social challenges.
2. To facilitate the quick acceptance of breaking-edge technologies and innovative services within European industry.
3. To promote new, integrated business models, combining multi-criteria and multi-sectoral approach among decision-makers.

Therefore, clear messages have been part of the VIBES story to face the concerns of European audiences aiming to reach at least 100,000 citizens, 1,500 EU industry professionals (at different levels, including technicians) in interconnected sectors and 500 decision makers (public such as legal entities and private such as company directors and business developers).

VIBES stems from cooperation within a European consortium between organisations based in different EU countries, allowing for better results to be achieved, which would have otherwise been impossible. The

project has validated better use of resources to demonstrate the high potential of the Circular Economy with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation has been based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology, based on the development of smart Bio-based materials, applied for the first time to thermoset composites), which will equip the Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor. In addition, the VIBES approach will wide open the door to the manufacturing industry to design and produce enhanced components to boost jobs, growth and investment at European level. Finally, the inter-sectoral relationships as well as the project’s shared objectives will influence the different decision makers, contributing to competitiveness and helping to meet social challenges.

The VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training plan guides the strategies that set the key messages that have been sent by the partnership as well as the target audience, including gender balance aspects. The strategies focus on target sectors related to the VIBES approach: composite materials, polymers, chemicals, logistics and transport, aeronautical, naval, energy and construction sectors among the main ones. To maximise the interest of the VIBES stakeholders, impact multipliers at the local, regional, national, European and global levels have been used (for instance, by taking advantage of networking with other identified BBI/CBE and H2020/Horizon Europe projects, BIC and BBI/CBE channels). In addition, for the project’s communication and dissemination activities, the consortium has identified media (press, magazines, digital media channels, thematic blogs, etc.) and events such as meetings, conferences, trade-fairs, workshops, training days, info-days, which are thematically close to the project. Moreover, a training plan has been aligned with the dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders for the envisaged new businesses and to science student profiles, in order to create a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.

1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables

This report serves to present the impact on communication and dissemination that the project is having in different areas. It includes the communication and dissemination activities implemented in Task 6.2 “Communication Implementation” and Task 6.3 “Dissemination Implementation” as well as the workshops, courses and training implemented in Task 6.4 “Training Implementation”. The Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities is a horizontal action and the input for all relevant activities comes from the results and deliverables of all the other project work packages that include research, validation, pilot implementation and innovation actions.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

With the above in mind, this final version of the Communication, Dissemination and Training activities report, includes the updated VIBES Communication, Dissemination and Training Strategy and Plan as well as the corresponding activities implemented during the whole duration of the project, structured in 8 distinct chapters, as follows:

Chapter 1 - Introduction: it provides information about the scope of the report, its structure and its relationship with other activities and deliverables.

Chapter 2 - Communication and Dissemination Strategy: it defines the strategy for dissemination and communication activities by outlining the objectives, the target audiences, with reference to the Stakeholders Board and synergies with other projects and initiatives, the key messages, the key exploitable results of VIBES, the partners' role and responsibilities and the gender dimension.

Chapter 3 - Communication Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels used for carrying out the communication activities of the project, including the VIBES visual identity and promotional material, VIBES website and social media accounts, e-newsletters and press kit, participation in fairs and info-days and the Layman's report at the end of the project.

Chapter 4 - Dissemination Means and Channels: it presents the different means and channels used for carrying out the dissemination activities of the project, including publications to scientific journals, participation in scientific conferences and events, organisation of events, such as forums, roundtables, workshops and final event.

Chapter 5 - Training Programme: it describes the training strategy and activities that took place during the whole duration of the project to spread the idea of VIBES to younger generations of scientists and to industrial professionals.

Chapter 6 – Time Frame of Communication, Dissemination and Training activities: it provides the time frame of the communication, dissemination and training activities of the project.

Chapter 7 - Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting: it presents the monitoring and reporting of the communication, dissemination and training activities, according to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set for those activities.

Chapter 8 - Conclusions: it summarises the final conclusions of the Communication, Dissemination and Training plan and activities throughout the whole duration of the project.

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overview and Objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of VIBES outlines the strategy that has been followed for every communication, dissemination and training activity implemented for the entire project duration. For that reason, it is a document that is largely connected with all the activities of the project's workplan.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy aimed at enabling wide reach and contributing to a positive impact of the project, both exploiting the knowledge within the consortium and transferring the gained knowledge further to interested stakeholders. This strategy defined clear guidelines for all the dissemination and communication activities, which have been carried out throughout the project.

The VIBES communication and dissemination strategy can be summed up into the following main objectives:

- Promote the project's concept, activities, and events to interested target groups and stakeholders.
- Enhance the awareness of the project's goals and outcomes.
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities.
- Encourage participation in relevant conferences and other events.
- Disseminate the project's results and knowledge gained to the public.
- Establish liaisons and synergies with other relevant initiatives.
- Facilitate market uptake of the project's results.
- Define partners' responsibilities in communication and dissemination activities.
- Organise training courses and workshops so that the ideas and outcomes of VIBES will be further developed by younger generations of scientists and industrial professionals.

To ensure a successful outcome of the objectives mentioned above, the VIBES communication and dissemination strategy focused on a practical and realistic plan including the appropriate means, channels and actions to spread the ideas of VIBES and engage the target audiences, but it also remained flexible and open to changes when necessary. The key element for a successful Communication and Dissemination Plan is a well-structured methodology based on **what we want to disseminate** (project assets), **to whom** (which target groups), **by what means** (press releases, social media, communication and dissemination tools, channels etc.), and **when to disseminate**. Keeping these in mind, the following steps emerged:

- Identify the project's aims and appropriate communication and dissemination channels to ensure maximum visibility.
- Identify the main target groups and appropriate communication and dissemination channels for each group.
- Identify the key messages and project's outcomes.
- Link communication and dissemination channels to each target group and define communication and dissemination tools and methods which have been used during the project.

- Establish the roles and responsibilities of the partners in executing and managing the project’s communication and dissemination activities.
- Determine the stages of the communication and dissemination activities and overall timeline.
- Monitor key communication and dissemination indicators and adjust when necessary.

2.2 Target Audiences, Key Messages and Key Results

2.2.1 The VIBES Target Audiences

All communication and dissemination activities have contributed to the overall aim of facilitating the widespread adoption of VIBES results, thus maximising the project’s impact. Therefore, it has been essential to clearly specify the VIBES target audiences.

The stakeholder groups that are illustrated in the following table have been identified as relevant to the VIBES project and, thus, represent the target audiences of the project’s communication and dissemination strategy.

Table 1. VIBES stakeholder groups and sub-groups

Group	Sub-group
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers
	Composite recyclers
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Aeronautical
	Naval
	Construction
	Energy
	Waste management
	Logistics
	Transport
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Academics and/or Researchers
	Technology and/or Innovation consultants
Impact multipliers	Policy makers
	Media/ journalists or bloggers

Group	Sub-group
	Relevant projects or initiatives

The identified stakeholder groups of the VIBES project are described below in more detail:

- **Industrial Developers:** industries that develop composite materials and/ or technologies for their recycling (thermoset composite material developers, composite recyclers).
- **Industrial Users:**
 - **Industrial Converters:** industries that manufacture equipment or build infrastructure, which includes parts made of composite materials, such as the aeronautical industry, the naval or shipbuilding industry, the construction and energy industries.
 - **Industrial Dismantlers:** companies that dismantle industrial facilities or infrastructure and are responsible for their waste management and disposal.
 - **Industrial End-users:** industries that use and/ or maintain equipment or infrastructure with parts made of composite materials, such as the transportation (airports, railway, shipping) and logistics sectors.
- **Academic Community:** researchers at universities and other research organisations working in the fields of materials science and engineering, composites, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling technologies, waste management, as well as other relevant disciplines (e.g. environmental sciences, social sciences, technical fields).
- **Technology and/or Innovation consultants:** organisations or individuals with expertise in technological and/ or commercial aspects of innovative technologies regarding sustainability and the circular economy.
- **Policy Makers:** decision-makers, EU and national level stakeholders, as well as the relevant standardisation and certification authorities, playing a key role in policy design, adoption and implementation, in the fields of the environment, waste management and circular economy.
- **Media/ Journalists or bloggers:** press or individual writers, specialised in relevant topics, such as new technologies and bioeconomy, waste management, circular economy.
- **Relevant projects or initiatives:** complementary EU actions and national or regional projects and initiatives within the EU bioeconomy and circular economy ecosystem (see section 2.2.3)

2.2.2 The VIBES Stakeholders Board

The VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB) includes individuals, either independent or representing organisations, who are external to the consortium partners. It is formed by a minimum number of 10 representatives, consisting of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings.

The members of the Stakeholders Board are strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. They

collaborate in the project to effectively respond to market and social needs, give feedback and better guide decisions in the project. They are industry-led, while fostering public and private collaboration.

The Stakeholders Board completes the whole value chain together with consortium partner members and is chaired by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN representative). Specific dissemination activities with members of the Stakeholders Board, including two roundtables and a demonstration workshop, have taken place (see sections 4.3.2 and 4.3.3) to share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept effectively. Key points from the activities of the project with the members of the Stakeholders Board are presented in the deliverable “D6.6 : Feedback on key points from stakeholders’ panel activities”.

The VIBES consortium partners have nominated individuals belonging to relevant stakeholder groups after initially contacting them informally, with the aim to be invited to participate in the Stakeholders Board.

After having received the initial informal interest and consent of the nominated individuals, the partners provided the following information to the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PAN), using an EXCEL file named “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” (see Annex 1):

- Stakeholder group/ sub-group that the nominated person belongs to (either chosen from the groups listed in the above Table 1 or by specifying another group/ sub-group)
- Contact name and gender of the nominated person
- Contact email
- Organisation name and website (if applicable)
- Country
- Consortium partner (name/ organisation) that nominated them
- To be invited as Stakeholders Board member (yes/ no/ maybe)
- Any comments (i.e. specifying if they are member(s) of a relevant project or initiative, a relevant working group or cluster etc.)

Following their initial informal interest and consent, the nominated stakeholders were officially invited by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board by signing the “Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form” (Annex 2), after having read and agreed to the “Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference” (Annex 3) and the [VIBES Privacy Policy](#) (available on the VIBES website). The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) followed up the communication with the nominated stakeholders and included them in the VIBES Stakeholders Board after having received the signed Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent form. Those who did not provide the signed form are not considered members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

The following figures show details about the final composition of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

Figure 1. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per stakeholder type

Figure 2. Number of VIBES Stakeholders Board members per country

Figure 3. Gender of VIBES Stakeholders Board members

2.2.3 Synergies with Other Projects and Initiatives

Synergies within the EU bioeconomy and circular economy ecosystem, as well as complementary EU actions and regional/ national projects and initiatives, have been pursued by all partners in the VIBES research domains and industry sectors, to facilitate knowledge exchange, gain mutual dissemination benefits and exploit potential co-operations.

The following Table presents an updated list of projects and initiatives that have been identified as being related to VIBES, some more closely than others.

Table 2. Projects/ initiatives related to VIBES

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
Horizon2020 Project	BIZENTE	A biocatalytic model of enzymatic degradation as a novel alternative to the end-of-life (landfill and incineration) of thermoset composites.
Horizon2020 Project	ECOXY	Bio-based, recyclable, re-shapable & repairable (3R) fibre reinforced thermoset composites.
Horizon2020 Project	polynSPIRE	Demonstration of innovative technologies towards a more efficient and sustainable plastic recycling
LIFE Project	LIFE RECYSITE	Demonstrating recyclability and reuse of a new generation of high-performance fibre-reinforced thermoset composites from renewable resources (bio-waste).
Horizon2020 Project	HELACS	Holistic processes for the cost-effective and sustainable management of End of Life of Aircraft Composite Structures.
	BAMCO	Design of bio-composites from bamboo fibres and biobased resins, either thermoplastic or thermosets.
Horizon2020Project	LIBRE	Development and demonstration of the feasibility of lignin-based carbon fibre materials for application in energy and automotive sectors.
European Association	SPIRE	European Association, bringing together cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, minerals and ores, non-ferrous metals, pulp and paper, refining, steel and water sectors, several being world-leading

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
		sectors operating from Europe.
Horizon Europe Project	CUBIC	Improving the circularity of complex plastic multi-material composites using novel biobased materials in B2B semi-finished products.
Horizon Europe Project	BIO UPTAKE	Ensure a sustainable uptake (increase the use in a 39%) of bioplastic composites through boosting a twin green and digital transformation in the European manufacturing industry.
Horizon Europe Project	EoLO-HUBs	Recovering glass and carbon fibre from wind turbine blades at the end of their useful lives and creating a knowledge hub to facilitate the recycling.
European Network	Clean Aviation	EU's leading research and innovation programme for transforming aviation towards a sustainable, climate-neutral future; an institutionalised European Partnership for Clean Aviation under Horizon Europe; building on the success of Clean Sky and Clean Sky 2.
European Network	2Zero	A co-programmed Partnership funded under the Horizon Europe programme and aiming at accelerating the transition towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility across Europe; promoting the delivery of green vehicles and mobility system solutions in Europe; building upon the successes of the European Green Cars Initiative (EGCI: 2009-2013) and the European Green Vehicles Initiative (EGVI: 2014-2020).
European Network	A.SPIRE/ P4Planet	Committed to manage and implement the Processes4Planet co-programmed Partnership. It represents innovative process industries, 20% of the total European manufacturing sector in employment and turnover, and more than 170 industrial and research process stakeholders from over a dozen countries spread throughout Europe. A.SPIRE brings together cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, minerals and ores, non-ferrous metals, pulp and

Type of project/ Initiative	Name	Description
		<p>paper, refining, steel and water sectors, several being world-leading sectors operating from Europe. The Processes4Planet (P4Planet) Partnership aim is to transform the European process industries to achieve circularity and overall climate neutrality at the EU level by 2050 while enhancing their global competitiveness. SPIRE has been the contractual Public-Private Partnership active between 2014 and 2020 and dedicated to innovation in resource and energy efficiency enabled by the process industries. The cPPP has been launched under the Horizon 2020 Programme by A.SPIRE - as the private entity - and the European Commission.</p>

The actions required to create synergies with relevant projects and initiatives were coordinated by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) with support from the rest of the consortium partners.

Synergies included participation in events of similar projects and initiatives, dissemination of VIBES promotional material in events of similar projects and initiatives, invitations to participate in VIBES events, exchange of news through each other’s channels, inclusion of the project’s website and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects and initiatives, provision of feedback in each project’s activities, etc.

Synergies with certain projects also included co-organisation of specific dissemination events, such as the demonstration workshops that were organised in collaboration with some of the projects and initiatives mentioned in Table 2, as described in Chapter 4, section 4.3.2.

2.2.4 The VIBES Key Messages

It has been very important for the VIBES Communication and Dissemination Strategy to define the fundamental messages of the project that have been communicated to the target audiences. A crucial point of the decided key messages is that they give a clear image of the project’s vision, but they are also tailored depending on the needs of each target group (e.g. industrial developers and industrial users who would be interested in the use of the VIBES developed materials and recycling technology, academics and scientists who would be interested in the scientific methods and results of VIBES and policy makers, the media and the general public, who are concerned about a greener economy and the protection of the environment).

Although these messages have been specified as the project progressed, based on the actual data and outcomes and the milestones achieved, a list of the main key messages of the project that have been communicated to each stakeholder group, including the means used, is provided in the following Table as a point of reference.

Table 3. Key messages and means used for VIBES targeted stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
Industry (developers and users)	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability. • Contributes to reduced use of primary materials and landfilling. • Produces added-value products for the circular economy. • Facilitates the use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns. • Provides new knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Leaflets • Infographic • Articles in industry magazines • Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days • COMPOSIFORUM international events • Demonstration workshops • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Roundtables • Layman’s report • Final conference
Academic and research community	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shares new knowledge and data on bio-based thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties. • Shares new knowledge and data on recycling technology based on green pre-treatments. • Provides new knowledge and skills for European students in materials science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Project social media • e-Newsletters • Scientific publications • Presentations in scientific conferences/ forums • COMPOSIFORUM international event • Research workshops for researchers and technicians • Summer courses for younger generation of scientists • Final conference

Stakeholder Group	Key Messages	Means
Policy makers	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreases the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. Boosts jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. Achieves better results through collaborative innovation, contributing to competitiveness and helping meet social challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentations in conferences, fairs and info-days COMPOSIFORUM international event Roundtables Layman’s report Final conference
Press General public	<p>VIBES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrates an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling solution. Returns products obtained from recycling process to the market. Boosts jobs, growth and investments with forward-looking policies for climate change. Provides new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Project social media e-Newsletters Leaflets Press releases and articles Digital media channels Promotional videos Layman’s report

2.2.5 The VIBES Key Exploitable Results

The VIBES project has specific exploitable results that can be of interest to different stakeholder groups and are disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective industrial users and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout. A list of VIBES key exploitable results is shown in the following Table.

Table 4. VIBES key exploitable results and outcomes

VIBES main results and outcomes
The VIBES bisphenol-free epoxy resins developed using biobased materials , also incorporating in certain cases Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM) that facilitate the reuse and revalorisation of the composites.
The VIBES lignin-derived carbon fibres and fabrics developed for sustainable reinforcement alternatives.
The VIBES thermoset composite panels produced and tested, using the newly developed bisphenol-free epoxy resins: three vitrimers-based (BBM) reinforced with glass, carbon and flax fibres for the naval industry , two others reinforced with glass and carbon fibres for the

VIBES main results and outcomes
construction industry.
The VIBES recyclable flax-reinforced composite produced and tested for non-structural components in the aeronautics industry.
The VIBES green recycling technology for thermoset epoxy-based composites, revolutionising the way thermoset composite materials are being revalorised.
The VIBES pilot plant for recycling thermoset composites , based on eco-friendly processes, with the potential to separate and revalorise composites from the construction, naval and aeronautics industries.
The VIBES valorised resins (monomers/oligomers) and fibres , recovered from the recycling process, demonstrating the potential of the green recycling technology to revalorise both reinforcement and matrix.
The VIBES industry-oriented protocols and manuals of new developed solutions, to be used for certification and authorisation of use.
The VIBES training course for industrial professionals on the circular economy for thermoset composites, to further develop the ideas and outcomes of VIBES.
The VIBES summer master classes for students on green composites, providing new knowledge and skills to the younger generation of scientists and engineers.
The VIBES brand and community of stakeholders , comprised of industrial developers and users of thermoset composite materials, the corresponding academic and research community, relevant technology & innovation experts, as well as policy makers, facilitating the dissemination and market uptake of VIBES results.

2.3 Role and Responsibilities

In order to achieve the aims and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, all members of the project consortium have played a key role during VIBES communication and dissemination activities. Partners' contribution has been a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones and progress either involve communication and dissemination activities and engagement or turn into communication and dissemination assets. Furthermore, partners have helped with the online presence of VIBES by providing content for the project news published on the website and the project's Social Media accounts. This contribution has been anything, from a Twitter post to an article reflecting on a VIBES dissemination activity, with the goal of creating a constant flow of content regarding project's actions.

Finally, partners have been encouraged to pursue the widest possible exposure of the project through their participation in relevant events/conferences, articles and publications in online/offline sources of information (e.g. websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.).

2.4 The Gender Dimension

The gender dimension has been integrated into the communication, dissemination and training strategy, including the establishment and monitoring of relevant indicators (see Table 10). Specific targets for the participation of women in certain communication, dissemination and training activities have been set, in order to guarantee gender balance and equality.

In particular, the gender dimension has been taken into consideration during the process of communicating with or selecting members and participants in various activities and events, as follows:

- In general, whenever possible, targeting communication and dissemination activities more intensely towards stakeholder groups that are represented by a fair number of female members.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board; in the final composition of the Stakeholders Board, 46% of its members are female (see figure 3 in section 2.2.2).
- Taking the gender aspect into account when approaching academics and researchers, technicians, industrial professionals, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders, in order to invite them to participate in the project's relevant events (i.e. forums, workshops, roundtables, training programme and final conference); it is estimated that in general at least 30% of the participants in such events were female.
- Taking the gender aspect into account when selecting the students for the summer training courses of the VIBES training programme, in which at least 30% of students were estimated to be female.

3. Communication Means and Channels

Communication activities aimed at increasing the public visibility of the project and its results using accessible language and suitable means and channels.

3.1 Visual Identity and Promotional Package

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) has been in charge of the preparation of VIBES visual identity and the graphic design and content of the digital and printable promotional material of VIBES.

The promotional material of the project has been mainly used at the project's events, external events where partners participated in and in the everyday publicity of the project.

3.1.1 Logo

By the end of the second month of the project, a project logo and visual identity were developed, in order to satisfy the visual and graphic requirements of the project. To achieve maximum visibility, the logo has

the capability to make the project recognisable and formed the basis for the design of all the promotional material, which has been used for the different promotional and communication activities of the project (e.g. leaflets, posters, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

The logo is represented on a friendly rounded font. The design involves the letter V which consists of 2 leaves; the green leaf refers to Green Solution and the purple leaf refers to Chemistry Innovation. The tag line connects the idea of Green Economy with that of Chemistry Innovation.

The logo colours (i.e. dark purple: #3C0F4B R: 60 / G: 15 / B:75 and light green: #23C887 R: 35 / G: 200 / B:135) are the colours of the project and have been used whenever possible to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.

The designed logo of VIBES, presented below with and without tag line, was adopted in agreement with all project partners.

Figure 4. VIBES logo with tag line

Figure 5. VIBES logo without tag line

Figure 6. The color codes of VIBES logo

In addition to the VIBES project logo, in any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc. produced in the frame of the project, the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) logo, combined with the Bio-based Industries Consortium logo and the Horizon2020 logo, has been shown.

Figure 7. The combined logo of Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking, Bio-based Industries Consortium and Horizon2020

The above combined logo has been accompanied by the following statement: “This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium”.

3.1.2 Leaflets

Leaflets are important tools to support the communication and dissemination activities of VIBES project to attract the interest of stakeholders from the various target audiences.

By the end of the third month of the project, the first leaflet was produced in electronic and printable formats. It introduced the VIBES aim and goals, the project phases, the expected results and benefits.

A second leaflet summarising project’s achievements was produced in electronic and printable formats at the mid-end of the project and was distributed through partners’ networks and at relevant events.

The leaflets also provide information about the consortium partners and the type of stakeholders involved, together with contact and website details and acknowledge the funding that the project receives through the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme. The leaflets are available in downloadable electronic format on the VIBES website. Furthermore, specifications on how to produce hard copies of the printable format of the leaflets were given to all partners. Each partner was responsible to produce the necessary number of printed copies of the leaflets to be available for distribution at various events that were organised in the frame of the project but also in external events, which partners participated in.

The first and second leaflets of the project are illustrated below. The recommended specifications for producing hard copies of the printable format of the leaflet are as follows:

- Tri-Fold
- Dimensions: 14X29cm (42X29cm open)
- Paper: Velvet 250gr
- Mat Varnish

Figure 8. The first leaflet of VIBES

In a Nutshell

VIBES presents an innovative solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, based on the development of a new green technology, focused on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components, by means of developing customised biobased bonding materials (BBM).

Products and services

- 100% Biobased Bonding Materials, specific for epoxy, polyester and vinyl resins.
- New 100% biobased resins (epoxy, polyester, vinyl) and fibres.
- Thermoset Composites with intrinsic recycling properties.
- New recycling technology for thermoset composites based on green pre-treatments.
- Valorised resins (monomers / oligomers) and fibres, recovered from recycling treatment.
- Training courses for industrial professionals on the circular economy for thermoset composites.
- Summer master classes for students on green composites.

Identity

Project title: Improving recyclability of thermoset composite materials through a greener recycling technology, based on reversible biobased bonding materials.

Grant Agreement No: 101023990
Starts: June 2021
Duration: 48 months
BBJ-U contribution: € 5,230,049.63

Find out more

VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu
CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu

FOLLOW US:
 Twitter: [@VIBES2021](https://twitter.com/VIBES2021)
 LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/vibes-project/
 Facebook: www.facebook.com/VIBESProject2021
 Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaU7w5y8V47LdnpR0Z8Q>

Project partners

	FUNDACION AITIP Research & Technology Organisation https://www.aitip.com/ Spain
	SPECIFIC POLYMERS Industrial Developer https://specificpolymers.com/ France
	ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRAENSE ASSOCIACION Research & Technology Organisation https://www.leitat.org/ Spain
	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK - Bernal Institute Academic Institution https://bernalinstitute.com/ Ireland
	DEUTSCHE INSTITUT FÜR TEXTIL UND FASERFORSCHUNG DESKUNENBERG Research & Technology Organisation https://www.ditf.de/en/ - Germany
	WEVERIJ FLIPTS EN DOBBELS NV Industrial Developer https://flisco.be/ Belgium
	BCIRCULAR COMPOSITES SOCIEDAD LIMITADA Industrial Developer https://www.bcircular.com/ Spain
	CONSORCIO AERODROMO AEROPUERTO DE TERUEL Industrial User http://www.aeropuertodeteruel.es/en/ Spain
	ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION SA Industrial User https://www.acciona.com/ Spain
	INGENIERIA Y DESARROLLOS EN COMPOSITE S.L. Industrial Developer http://www.idec.com/ Spain
	JUNO COMPOSITES LTD Industrial Developer https://juno-composites.com/ Ireland
	LABORATORI ARCHA SRL Technology Consultant http://www.archa.it/ Italy
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS FC Innovation Management Consultant https://qplan-intl.gr/ Greece

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101023990.

VIBES Green Chemistry Recyclability

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology.

www.vibesproject.eu

Aim

Develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, with the aim of decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

Project Goals

- Design and develop at least three 100% biobased bonding materials (BBM) for thermoset composites with tailored debonding functionalities.
- Design and develop at least three 100% biobased thermoset composite materials.
- Validate the thermoset composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties for optimum performance / cost ratio, in three high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.
- Design and implement a green recycling technology at pilot semi-industrial environment to separate and valorise the composite components as new feedstocks for the development of new products.
- Assess the life cycle impact of the developed products from environmental, social and economic point of view.
- Develop an exploitation & IPR strategy for Key Exploitable Results.
- Develop a Business Plan to demonstrate the commercial potential of the developed solution and describe how this potential will be realised.
- Inform, promote, communicate and disseminate the project objectives, activities and results; engage stakeholders to create synergies.
- Provide new knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

Stakeholders

The VIBES project covers the whole composites value chain by taking into account, apart from the consortium partners, the Stakeholders Board and interaction with other projects of Biobased Industries through communication and dissemination activities:

- Industrial developers: thermoset composite developers, composite recyclers.
- Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users: aeronautical, naval, construction and energy industries; waste management; logistics and transport.
- Technology & innovation experts: academic / researchers; technology and innovation consultants.
- Impact multipliers: policy makers; media / journalists or bloggers.

Project Phases

Phase 1: Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)	Phase 2: Biobased Thermoset Composite Components	Phase 3: Inherent Recyclable Thermoset Composites	Phase 4: Recycling Technology Development	Phase 5: Sustainability and Commercial Exploitation
Three different approaches	Biobased substitutes for resins	Design and synthesis	Collection and direction to recycling	Sustainability and economical assessment
Exploring combinations and synergies	Biobased fibres and surface treatments	Technical validation tests	Handling, toxicity and safety evaluation	Aligning with Green Deal and climate neutral strategy
Upscaling best BBM	New fabrics for composite applications	Testing debonding treatments	Recycling technology design	Involvement of supply chain & EPR considerations
	Upscaling best composite components	Valorisation of recovered fractions	Pilot recycling plant	Exploitation & IPR management
		Upscaling into high added-value products		Building a business case
Phase 6: Communication, Dissemination and Training	Communication, dissemination and training plan.	Communication campaign and dissemination actions.	Stakeholders' engagement, creating synergies.	Providing knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

www.vibesproject.eu

Benefits

- Improved properties of thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, leading to reduced environmental impact, combined with higher cost-effectiveness and increased profitability.
- Reduced use of primary materials and landfilling.
- Use of thermoset composite materials in industrial sectors without restrictions or environmental concerns.
- New knowledge for the European Industry on the circular economy for thermoset composite materials.
- New knowledge and skills for European students in material science, engineering and chemical fields, for new arising demand in technical jobs.
- Increased jobs and turnover by promoting two new industrial sector interconnections in the newly created "Intrinsic Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain":
 - Interconnection between waste management and biotechnology sectors.
 - Interconnection between thermoset composites and biotechnology sectors.

Figure 9. The second leaflet of VIBES

In a nutshell

VIBES introduces and showcases an innovative, eco-friendly, cost-effective, and non-toxic recycling technology, designed to reduce the disposal and environmental release of non-biodegradable polymers by at least 40%. After optimising and scaling the technology to a semi-industrial pilot level, the resulting products from this advanced recycling process will be reintroduced into the market. They will be valorised as new feedstocks for various chemicals or building blocks that can be upcycled into new industrial products.

Key Exploitable Results

- ✓ **Biobased, recyclable epoxy resins** incorporating specific **biobased bonding materials (BBMs)**, designed for use in **thermoset composites** with built-in **recycling capabilities**.
- ✓ **Advanced technology** for scaling up **lignin-TPU biobased carbon fibre**, intended for integration into **thermoset composites** with inherent **recycling properties**.
- ✓ **Environmentally friendly chemical recycling process** for **thermoset composites**, applicable at the end of their life cycle.

Project partners

	FUNDACION AITIP Research & Technology Organisation www.aitip.com Spain
	SPECIFIC POLYMERS Industrial Developer www.specificpolymers.com France
	LEITAT Research & Technology Organisation www.leitat.org Spain
	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK - Bernal Institute Academic Institution www.bernalinstitute.com Ireland
	DEUTSCHE INSTITUT FÜR TEXTIL UND FASERFORSCHUNG DOKENDORF Research & Technology Organisation www.ditf.de Germany
	WEVERIJ FLUPTS EN DOBBELS NV Industrial Developer www.flufts-dobbel.be Belgium
	BCIRCULAR COMPOSITES SOCIEDAD LIMITADA Industrial Developer www.bcircular.com Spain
	CONSORCIO AERODROMO AEROPUERTO DE TERUEL Industrial User www.aeropuertoteruel.com Spain
	ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION SA Industrial User www.accionacon.com Spain
	INGENIERIA Y DESARROLLOS EN COMPOSITE S.L. Industrial Developer www.idec-zero.com Spain
	JUNO COMPOSITES LTD Industrial Developer www.junocomposites.com Ireland
	LABORATORI ARCHA SRL Technology Consultant www.archa.it Italy
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC Innovation Management Consultant www.qplan-intl.gr Greece

VIBES

Green Chemistry Recycling Solution

An eco-friendly chemical recycling solution for the end-of-life management of thermoset composites

www.vibesproject.eu

Identity

Project title: Improving recyclability of thermoset composite materials through a greener recycling technology, based on reversible biobased bonding materials.
Grant Agreement No: 101023190
Start: 1 June 2021
Duration: 48 months
BBJ-JU contribution: € 4,224,039.25

Find Out More

VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu

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VIBES Project

VIBES Project

This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement N° 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Context and Rationale

Thermoset composites have emerged as key components across various industries—thanks to their high strength, durability, chemical resistance, and light weight, alongside excellent corrosion resistance. Their appeal spans sectors like aeronautics, automotive, construction, naval, energy, and more.

However, thermoset composites present a significant challenge at the end of their lifecycle. Due to their complexity, they are difficult to recycle, with most waste being either incinerated (42.6%) or sent to landfills (24.9%). As industrial demand for high-performance materials continues to rise, establishing a circular ecosystem for these composites is becoming crucial. This will be essential to aligning with the EU's 2050 climate-neutral strategy.

Aim

The VIBES project presents an innovative solution to improve the recyclability of thermoset composite materials through an innovative, eco-friendly, cost-effective, and non-toxic recycling technology.

At the core of VIBES lies the mission to transform the thermoset composite materials industry, strategically incorporating these materials into a circular economy framework.

Our Goal

At least 40% less waste

Project Phases

Communication, Dissemination, Training and Exploitation of project results

Project Achievements

Innovative breakthroughs in R&D

- **Bisphenol-free epoxy resins** developed using **biobased materials**, also incorporating in certain cases **Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)** that facilitate the reuse and revalorisation of the composites.
- **Lignin-derived carbon fibres** and fabrics developed for **sustainable reinforcement alternatives**.
- Introduced a **green recycling technology** for thermoset epoxy-based composites, revolutionising the way thermoset composite materials are being revalorised.

Real-world demonstrations of advanced solutions

- **Thermoset composite panels** produced and tested, using the newly developed bisphenol-free epoxy resins: three vitrimer-based (BBM) reinforced with glass, carbon and flax fibres for the **naval industry**, two others reinforced with glass and carbon fibres for the **construction industry**.
- A recyclable flax-reinforced composite produced and tested for non-structural components in the **aeronautics industry**.
- **Pilot plant** established for **recycling thermoset composites**, based on eco-friendly processes, with the potential to separate and revalorise composites from the construction, naval and aeronautics industries.
- **Recovered resins and fibres** valorised, demonstrating the potential of the green recycling technology to revalorise both reinforcement and matrix.

Successful stakeholder engagement and outreach

- 2 stakeholder roundtables, fostering collaboration with the industry and enlarging the **industrial impact** of the project.
- 2 summer courses for students, also adopted in e-learning format, and 4 training workshops for researchers and industry professionals, empowering the workforce.
- 9 scientific publications, 3 articles in industry magazines, and presentations at multiple conferences and workshops.

Stakeholders

The VIBES project addresses the entire composites value chain, incorporating not only consortium partners but also the VIBES Stakeholders Board and collaboration with other projects of Biobased Industries through communication and dissemination efforts. It ensures comprehensive engagement with a wide range of relevant stakeholders, including:

- Thermoset composite developers
- Industrial end-users across sectors such as aeronautics, naval, and construction
- Industrial waste management, logistics, and transport professionals
- Technology and innovation experts, including academics, researchers, and consultants
- Impact multipliers such as policymakers and media

This broad engagement strategy aims to maximise impact and drive innovation throughout the industry ecosystem.

Benefits

- Enhanced thermoset composite materials and recycling technology, reducing environmental impact while boosting cost-effectiveness and profitability.
- Lower reliance on primary materials and minimised landfill usage.
- Unrestricted industrial use of thermoset composites without environmental concerns.
- Fresh insights into the circular economy for thermoset composites within the European industry.
- Advanced skills and knowledge for European students in material science, engineering, and chemistry, meeting the rising demand for technical expertise.
- Job creation and economic growth through new connections in the "Intrinsic Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain":
 - Linking waste management with biotechnology.
 - Connecting thermoset composites with biotechnology.

3.1.3 Infographic

To add to the communication promotional package available for the communication activities of VIBES project, an infographic was created by the end of the fifth month of the project. The infographic has the purpose of explaining the VIBES solution on recycling composites to a public audience and can be used in stands or booths. It has been produced in electronic and printable formats, following the same overall layout designed for the project, and it is also available for downloading from the VIBES website.

The infographic has been designed to be produced as a poster or as a roll up banner. The recommended specifications for producing hard copies of the printable formats of the infographic are as follows:

- Poster:
 - Dimensions: A3 (29.70X42cm) and A0 (84.10X11.89cm)
 - Paper: Velvet 200gr
- Roll Up banner:
 - Dimensions: 80X200cm
 - Paper: Velvet 200gr

Figure 10. The infographic of VIBES in a poster form

Figure 11. The infographic of VIBES in a roll up form

3.1.4 Promotional Videos

By the end of the fifth month of the project, the **first promotional video** was produced to raise awareness and to exploit viral effects. The video was uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and the project’s website and was shared on the other Social Media Accounts of the project. This short video gives an overview of the project and its objectives, and it presents the main actions of the VIBES project.

The **second promotional video** was produced towards the end of the project (month 46), to raise awareness on project achievements and outcomes. It was also uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and the project’s website and was shared on the other Social Media Accounts of the project. In this video, team members of the VIBES project consortium present their role in the project highlighting their main achievements.

Figure 12. The story board of the VIBES first promotional video

(Source: [VIBES first promotional video](#))

13 The introduction of VIBES project

← reducing the negative impact of their waste on the environment.

14 The VIBES new green technology

← It is based on the development of a new green technology...

15 The VIBES new green technology

← focused on the controlled separation...

16 The VIBES new green technology

← and recovery of compatible material components.

17 The VIBES new green technology

← by means of developing contained...

18 The VIBES new green technology

← obtained bonding materials.

BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

19 The aim of the new green technology

← The new cost-efficient and non-toxic recycling technology solution...

COST-EFFICIENT NON-TOXIC

20 The aim of the new green technology

← allow to decrease the amount of non biodegradable polymers sent to incineration.

21 The aim of the new green technology

← or discharged to the environment as a base resin.

40% LESS WASTE

22 The obtained products

← The products obtained from the recycling process will return to the market...

23 The obtained products

← by means of their reutilization as raw materials for different chemicals or building blocks.

24 The obtained products

← used to recycling into new industrial products.

NEW INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTS

25 The growth benefits

← benefits will be significant also in terms of growth increasing sales.

26 The growth benefits

← will be achieved by promoting the use industrial and/or agricultural waste in the large industry.

27 The growth benefits

← "Technic: Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain"

28 The Consortium

← The VIBES project is a joint action.

29 The Consortium

← 13 partners from 7 EU member states, part of BBI4ed Industrial Cluster, participating under Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme of the European Union.

DESIGN

30 The activities

← The VIBES consortium achieves the project objectives by collaborating in a series of design.

DEVELOPMENT

31 The activities

← Development.

COMMUNICATION

32 The activities

← Communications.

TRAINING

33 The activities

← Lead training activities.

34 The stakeholders

← Moreover, the project brings together Stakeholders from the whole value chain who effectively respond to market and social needs.

35 The stakeholders

← User feedback.

36 The stakeholders

← Lead better guide decisions in the project.

Want to keep up to date?

37 Call to action

← Want to keep up to date? Visit our website or follow us on social media.

38 Pack size

← VIBES Green Chemistry Recycling Solution

Narration

Over recent years, more and more high technology industries increase the use of thermoplastic materials to create strong and durable products. However, the use of these non-biodegradable composite materials poses a technical difficulty due to their inherent complexity, generating plastic waste. Unfortunately, most of this waste is not properly recycled, so there is a priority to Europe to develop a systematic circular economy.

The VIBES project presents an innovative solution to reduce the level of life cycles of thermoplastic composite materials, reducing the negative impact of their waste in the environment.

The new, low-cost and easy-to-use recycling technology solution aims to improve the use of non-biodegradable materials used in digital and analogic applications.

The product obtained from the recycling process will result in the reuse of these materials as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks and by applying the new industrial processes.

Benefits will be significant also in terms of growth, increasing sales and turnover by generating low-cost industrial-scale innovations in the more robust thermoplastic Thermoplastic Composite Resin (TRC).

The VIBES project is a joint action of 13 partners from 7 EU member states, part of BBI4ed Industrial Cluster, participating under Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme of the European Union.

The VIBES consortium achieves the project objectives by collaborating in a series of design, development, communication and training activities. Moreover, the project brings together Stakeholders from the whole value chain who effectively respond to market and social needs, give feedback and better guide decisions in the project.

Want to keep up to date? Visit our website or follow us on social media.

VIBES

Green Chemistry Recycling Solution

VIBES has received funding from the BBI4ed Industrial Cluster (contracting under the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101012210).

Figure 13. VIBES team members present their role and achievements

(Source: [VIBES second promotional video](#))

3.1.5 Document and Presentation Templates

With a view to design an easily recognisable graphical identity for the project, the following templates have been developed and updated:

- Presentation template in PowerPoint, that has been used as a basis for the various presentations created during the project, either for internal or external communication.
- Document template in MSWord, that has been used as a basis for the project deliverables and reports.
- Letterhead template in MSWord, that has been used for communication with project stakeholders and other written communication about the project.

These templates are shown in Annex 4.

3.1.6 Image Galleries

Image galleries have been used as visual promotional material in communication activities, for instance when posting news on the project website and social media or in project presentations and articles and the Layman’s report. The image galleries include the following types of images:

- Pictures of VIBES related technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities, mainly used in newsletters and news on the project website.

- Images using the VIBES visual identity and colours including short promotional text and/ or relevant icons, mainly used when posting news on the project website and social media.
- Pictures or screenshots of project meetings, mainly used when posting relevant news on social media.

A repository of images has been created, including pictures of relevant technologies and products, processes, teams and facilities, shared by several consortium partners.

Figure 14. Images of VIBES News

3.2 VIBES Website

The project website (www.vibesproject.eu) is a key communication tool to increase the project visibility and impact, presenting the progress of the project to wider audiences. The VIBES website was launched in the fourth month of the project and serves as the online platform for public and consortium communication. The structure and content of the website have been designed to ensure ease of use and clearly reports the project's concept and objectives but will also contain relevant information about its progress, with news and event announcements.

Q-PLAN is the partner responsible for the design, development, maintenance, and management of the website. Special attention has been paid to a type of website that is responsive and accessible via and compatible with a variety of devices, including mobile devices.

Beside the key information presented, the project website includes all publishable project's outcomes, promotional material, reports, publications, deliverables and further resources of interest. The website reflects the work happening in the context of VIBES. All partners were, hence, expected to contribute to the content development process with news and updates. The website regularly reported on project's activities, internal and external events, findings, publishable outcomes, information about partners and similar projects/initiatives, as well as other news that are relevant to the project and its development.

The full structure and content of the VIBES website is presented in deliverable D6.1 "Project Website". The website sitemap is illustrated below:

- Home page
- About:
 - Concept and objectives
 - Consortium partners
 - Stakeholders
 - Activities
- Resources:
 - Reports
 - Publications
 - Training material
 - Promotional material
 - Other links (relevant events, relevant projects)
- News & Events:
 - Project developments
 - Dissemination and training events
 - Newsletters
 - Press Releases
- Contact us
- Privacy Policy
- Private area (link to MSTeams collaborative space for VIBES)

The above-mentioned points constitute a baseline for the website. The content and information posted on the website has been updated regularly, to be in line with the project's requirements and progress. The URL for the website is www.vibesproject.eu and the contact email for the project is in line with it (info@vibesproject.eu).

Figure 15. Google analytics presenting the users (visitors) of the website

3.3 Social Media Accounts

The Social Media Accounts have been valuable tools, acting as one of the main pillars to promote the project and its activities. More specifically, an X (former Twitter) account, a LinkedIn account and a Facebook account were launched during the first month of the project, whereas a YouTube account was created during the third month of the project, aiming to build an online community of supporters and followers that will continue to exist beyond the duration of the project.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) has been responsible for the administration of VIBES social media accounts. However, all partners contributed by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile).
- Promoting the accounts in their networks.
- Suggesting relevant profiles that VIBES should connect with.
- Promoting posts and news through the social media accounts of their own organisations.

Table 5. VIBES social media accounts

Social Media Platform	Name of Account	URL
X (Twitter)	@VIBESU2	https://twitter.com/VIBESU2
LinkedIn	vibes-project	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vibes-project/
Facebook	VIBESProject2021	https://www.facebook.com/VIBESProject2021

Social Media Platform	Name of Account	URL
YouTube	VIBES Project	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCauYtwBy8V47hLdnpzROZ8Q

Once or twice per week, the project’s social media have been updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organisations / associations that promote activities and technologies relevant to VIBES, news from related EU projects etc.

The YouTube channel has been updated, including the first promotional video of VIBES that was published in the fifth month of the project, the VIBES Summer Course video that was published in the twenty-eighth month of the project, the second promotional video of VIBES that was published in the forty-sixth month of the project, and a video presenting the VIBES Layman’s Report, published in the forty-seventh month of the project.

Screenshots of the VIBES presence on social media accompanied with analytics regarding the followers and the engagement (X, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube) are presented in Annex 5.

3.4 E-Newsletters

The project produced a bi-annual electronic newsletter (8 issues in total), covering the activities developed every semester of the project’s lifespan. When needed, the timing of the launch of a newsletter issue was adapted to announce special events. The newsletter issues were distributed to the project’s target audience, including all those who subscribed to it via the project website, and they have also been uploaded to the project website. Moreover, the project launched the addition of a [LinkedIn Newsletter](#) as a strategic action to enhance the dissemination of the VIBES newsletter. The newsletter summarised updates on the project’s developments and actions and represented an alternative way to inform potential and/or existing followers with regards to the project’s concepts. Furthermore, the newsletter was a way to attract and retain stakeholders that are not familiar with social media or people who were not interested enough during the initial phases of the project, to keep them connected and try to engage them at a later stage.

The newsletter issues were prepared by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager, with the contribution of all partners to specific content when necessary. Although the content of each newsletter issue has been agreed upon in collaboration with project partners, the newsletter mainly includes the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the VIBES project
- Progress updates
- A project’s news section, including articles that describe the main activities carried out during the latest semester
- A section dedicated to future developments (e.g. upcoming events), when needed
- A section listing other relevant major events, when needed
- Other types of relevant articles, if available

The final newsletter was accompanied by a feedback questionnaire for recipients to indicate the level of impact on them from information on project progress, achievements and recommendations.

All eight issues of the VIBES electronic newsletter, which were published and disseminated, can be found on the project website in the [Newsletters](#) section. Indicatively, the last two issues of the VIBES e-newsletter, including the feedback questionnaire, are presented in Annexes 6 and 7.

3.5 Press Kit

3.5.1 Press Releases and Articles

Nine (9) general press releases were produced, either every six months and/or on an ad-hoc basis, especially when outcomes, progress and important actions were achieved, targeting stakeholders at the EU level. The general press releases aimed to inform stakeholders about the overall project actions and results, but they also incorporated space for featuring specific stories related to project achievements in the form of additional short articles, produced by various project partners that have them published in local media. The press releases were produced after each project meeting or prior to a project event with the purpose of attracting local media attention.

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager was in charge of preparing each general press release, but every partner was responsible for translating the press releases into their local language and communicate them to their local press or via their own digital channels (partners websites and/ or social media).

All nine general press releases, which were produced and published, are available on the project website in the [Press Releases](#) section. The first general press release was launched after the project kick-off meeting to announce the beginning of the project and introduce the project's goals and partners. The second general press release was launched after the launch of the project website to attract the interest of stakeholders to visit the project website, subscribe to the electronic newsletter and follow VIBES on social media. The third general press release was launched following the 1st year anniversary of the project, outlining the project progress during the first year and the next steps. The fourth, fifth, sixth, seventh and eighth general press releases were launched following the consortium project meeting of each semester, referring to the project progress. The ninth general press release was launched following the project's final event, outlining the project's key achievements and impact. Indicatively, the last two press releases of VIBES are presented in Annexes 8 and 9.

3.5.2 Digital Media Channels

In an effort to reach a wider audience and promote the innovative concepts of bioeconomy and circular economy, our project partners have been actively engaged in digital platforms for dissemination.

BCIRC showcased the project's impact in an episode of Energy Trends in the podcast broadcast on 28th March 2022 with the title "Circular economy: a paradigm that proposes rethinking the way we design, produce and consume". In this [podcast](#) Oriol Grau, head of BCIRC, debates with Edith Guedella, Head of the road and environment group at ACCIONA, Francisco Ruiz, Director of Business Consulting for NTT DATA and Iñigo Vegas, Director of the Cement Based Products Business Area at Tecnalia, about the new sustainable materials of the future, using the VIBES project as an example.

Furthermore, Teruel Airport (PLATA) generated a video in the platform INDUSTRY TALKS on 5th October 2021 with the title [Sustainable Innovation in Aeronautic Sector](#), in which the VIBES project was introduced. That platform has 1660 subscribers, so its scope is very interesting for VIBES.

In addition to leveraging digital platforms, the project coordinator AITIIP shared insightful results of the VIBES project at [Veltha's](#) LOOPS 3.0 second [webinar](#), titled "Composites for the Circular Economy: VIT meets VIBES," held on 22nd January, 2024. This activity demonstrates further the VIBES consortium commitment to disseminating the project's advancements effectively.

Figure 16. Alejandro Ibrahim (PLATA) I-Talks

Figure 17. AITIIP at LOOPS webinar

3.6 Articles in Press and Industry Magazines

So that the project reaches a broader audience and makes the VIBES objectives and achievements known to its industrial stakeholders who belong to a wide range of industries and services, the project partners have been encouraged to submit their findings as articles in relevant magazines, both locally and internationally.

The following Table lists the articles about VIBES that have been published in local press and industry magazines.

Table 6. Articles about VIBES in local press and industry magazines

Partner	Date	Name of magazine / newspaper	Type	Link
ULIM	19/06/2021	Limerick Leader	General	https://www.limerickleader.ie/news/news/642549/groundbreaking-research-at-ul-helps-develop-cheaper-and-more-sustainable-carbon-fibre.html
AITIIP	23/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/aragon/2021/06/23/vibes-un-proyecto-europeo-que-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion-1501499.html
AITIIP	23/6/2021	Mundoplast	Plastic sector	https://mundoplast.com/proyecto-vibes-reciclar-compuestos-termoestables/
AITIIP	23/06/2021	InterEmpresas	Business, focused on technology	https://www.interempresas.net/Nautica/Articulos/354671-AITIIP-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-aeronautica.html
AITIIP	24/06/2021	Química y Sociedad	Chemical sector	https://www.quimicaysociedad.org/aitiip-lidera-el-proyecto-vibes-que-desarrollara-una-tecnologia-ecologica-para-reciclar-piezas-termoestables-en-los-sectores-naval-aeronautico-y-construccion/
AITIIP	25/06/2021	Heraldo de Aragón	General	

Partner	Date	Name of magazine / newspaper	Type	Link
AITIIP	26/06/2021	Retema	Environmental sector	https://www.retema.es/noticia/espana-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-tecnologia-para-reciclar-compuestos-plasti-xKnJT
AITIIP	28/06/2021	Construible	Sustainable construction	https://www.construible.es/2021/06/28/vibes-desarrollara-tecnologia-ecologica-reciclar-polimeros-reutilizarlos-construccion
AITIIP	02/07/2021	Gestores de Recursos	Waste management	https://gestoresderesiduos.org/noticias/un-proyecto-europeo-con-participacion-espanola-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion
AITIIP	04/07/2021	Aragón Digital	General	https://www.aragondigital.es/2021/07/04/el-centro-tecnologico-aitiip-lidera-un-proyecto-para-desarrollar-una-tecnologia-ecologica-de-reciclaje-de-piezas/
AITIIP	04/07/2021	Aragón Press	General	http://aragonpress.com/pages/noticia.asp?notid=598423
AITIIP	07/07/2021	Diario de Teruel	General	https://www.diariodeteruel.es/teruel/el-aeropuerto-de-teruel-socio-en-un-proyecto-de-reciclaje-de-piezas-42551
DITF	26/07/2021	Dezeen	General	https://www.dezeen.com/2021/07/26/carbon-bio-based-carbon-fibres/
AITIIP	04/08/2021	Tecnología Circular	Circular economy, technology and innovation	https://www.tecnologiacircular.cl/2021/08/proyecto-europeo-busca-soluciones-al-reciclaje-de-piezas-de-avion/
ULIM	12/10/2021	Composites	Industry	https://www.compositesworld.com/ne

Partner	Date	Name of magazine / newspaper	Type	Link
		World		ws/university-of-limerick-seeks-to-improve-composites-recycling-solutions
ULIM	02/11/2021	Silicon Republic	General	https://www.siliconrepublic.com/innovation/ul-composite-materials-vibes-project-horizon-2020-eu
ULIM	05/11/2021	The Clare Herald	General	https://clareherald.com/2021/11/05/ul-leads-way-on-composites-recycling-solution-73452/
ULIM	16/12/2021	Innovation in Textiles	Industry	https://www.innovationintextiles.com/composites/towards-recyclable-composite-materials/
AITIIP	08/2022	RETEMA	Environmental sector	Revista digital Julio/Agosto 2022 - Especial Residuos RETEMA
AITIIP	10/2022	AVEP	Industry	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BgraPLAXop10rLPhbpi4ACYxnZ20lice/view
AITIIP	01/2023	Easy Engineering Magazine	Industry	https://easyengineering.eu/interview-with-aitiip-technology-centre/
BCIRC	03/2023	Interempresas	General	https://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/470785-Entrevista-a-Oriol-Grau-CEO-de-BCircular.html
F&D	30/10/2024	JEC News	Industry	https://www.jeccomposites.com/news/by-jec/flipts-dobbels-opens-new-pathways-for-biocomposites-within-vibes-initiative/

3.7 Participation in Events/ Fairs/ Info-days

Participating in relevant events and fairs are unique opportunities to reach further audiences with a wide range of backgrounds. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners have planned to participate in at least 6 external events and fairs with a view to:

- present VIBES concept,
- keep in touch with the latest advances,
- share knowledge,
- establish contacts and interactions with stakeholders,
- promote VIBES actions and results,
- raise awareness.

To ensure consistency in the presentation and communication of the project, partners had at their disposal a common leaflet, a template for presentation slides, an infographic that could be produced as a poster or roll up, and a template for publications, all of which incorporate the VIBES logo and colours.

The consortium partners have been very active in their participation in relevant events and fairs, presenting VIBES among other projects and activities. The total target of participation in external events and fairs has been reached and surpassed. The following table lists the external events and fairs, in which partners have participated, presenting VIBES.

Table 7. Presentation of VIBES at relevant events

Partner	Date	Type of event / Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
AITIIP	25/09/2020	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to Isover-Saint Gobain.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/09/2020	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to VEOLIA (Water, waste and energy management services).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	26/03/2021	Online pitch event / Presentation of circular economy projects to Grupo Antolín (car sector supplier).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	03/04/2001	Online pitch event / Presentation to DGA (Government of Autonomous Community of Aragón)	Policy Makers	Spain
AITIIP	16/04/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of circular economy projects to Suez.	Industry	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event / Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
PLATA	08/05/2021	Presentation in Jaume I University about the participation of PLATA in European Projects, including VIBES, and PLATA's role in the innovation chain.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	20/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of circular economy projects to EDA (European Defence Agency).	Industry	Spain
PLATA	24/05/2021	Presentation in Space Port Master Plan Universidad de Cataluña about the participation of PLATA in European Projects, including VIBES, and PLATA's role in the innovation chain.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	25/05/2021	Online pitch event/ Presentation of circular economy projects to Finsa (Wood transformation company).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/06/2021	Workshop on bridging the gap between academia and industry: training in European digitalization and circular economy projects/ Presentation of the project at Spanish Industry (CAAR).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/07/2021	Online pitch event / Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to Airbus.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	29/09/2021	Pitch event / Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to Siemens-Gamesa.	Industry	Spain
ARCHA	26-29/10/2021	Exhibitor in the ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES, and distributing 200 copies of VIBES	Industry	Italy

Partner	Date	Type of event / Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		leaflets.		
PLATA	23/11/2021	Commercial presentation to the local event "Acto inauguración curso académico UNED".	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	29/11/2021	Presentation of VIBES objectives and expected results to industry, research centres and other institutions related to Horizon Europe at the workshop "Horizon Europe Clusters 6 and 5 opportunities in 2022".	Industry	Spain
AITIIP, ACCIONA	03-05/05/2022	Attendance of JEC World 2022 Exhibition, where the VIBES project was introduced to some of their contacts and visitors to the fair.	Industry	Paris
ARCHA	24-26/05/2022	Exhibitor in the Packaging Première & PCD Milan (Italy), where the experience gained during European Research & Innovation activities and projects, including VIBES, was described.	Industry	Italy
PLATA	15/07/2022	Presentation of VIBES in the aeronautical Course of University of Zaragoza	Students and workers	Spain
PLATA	24/09/2022	Presentation of VIBES in the Congress on Spatial rockets of the University of Zaragoza	Industry	Spain
BCIRC	18-20/10/2022	Presentation of VIBES at the Advanced Manufacturing Madrid 2022 Fair.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	15 - 17/02/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Transfiere 2023 Exhibition.	Civil Society	Spain
AITIIP	30/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES research line at the "Foro Wake Up Spain!" event.	Technical	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event / Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
BCIRC	30/03/2023	Participation to the Strategic Immersion Day "Roadmap 2030 for a Sustainable Economy".	Industry	Barcelona, Spain
AITIIP, F&D	25-27/04/2023	Participation to the "JEC World 2023" event, where the VIBES project was introduced to the visitors of the fair.	Industry	Paris
Q-PLAN	26/04/2023	Presentation of VIBES objectives, activities and expected results to European Business and Innovation Centre Network (EBN) / Sustainability, Agrifood and Health Special Interest Group meeting, to attract the interest of relevant innovation intermediaries in Europe.	Industry	Europe
PLATA	12/05/2023	Participation to the TARMAC ARAGON FACILITIES meeting, presenting VIBES.	Industry	Spain
ARCHA	16-18/05/2023	Exhibitor in the "Packaging Première & PCD Milan" exhibition ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES.	Industry	Milan, Italy
AITIIP	17/05/2023	Participation to the "Meetech Spain" exhibition, where the VIBES project was introduced to the visitors of the exhibition.	Industry	Madrid, Spain
ARCHA	7-10/10/2023	Exhibitor in the ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES.	Industry	Rimini, Italy
JUNO	01/11/2023	Presentation to End User discussing decarbonisation within the marine sector and presenting VIBES	Industry	United Kingdom

Partner	Date	Type of event / Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		technology.		
AITIIP	15/12/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the workshop “The end of a product, the beginning of a material”, organised by Xunta Galicia (Government).	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	20/03/2024	Presentation of VIBES at the Transfiere 2024 Exhibition.	Industry	Málaga
ACCIONA	5-7/04/2024	Presentation of VIBES at JEC World 2024 Fair.	Industry	Paris
PLATA	13/05/2024	Presentation of VIBES at summer courses in Teruel by Fundación Gargallo.	Students	Spain
PLATA	18/07/2024	Visit at Teruel Airport and meeting with the Spanish Association of Composite Materials AEMAC.	Industry	Spain
ARCHA	5-8/11/2024	Exhibitor in the ECOMONDO FAIR (Rimini, Italy), presenting European Research & Innovation activities and projects to visitors, including VIBES.	Industry	Rimini, Italy
AITIIP	4-6/03/2025	Presentation of VIBES at AITIIP’s stand in JEC World 2025 event.	Industry	Paris
Q-PLAN	13-15/03/2025	VIBES was showcased among other projects at Q-PLAN's stand in “Forward Green”, an International Exhibition on Circular Economy.	Industry Policy Makers	Thessaloniki, Greece
PLATA & AITIIP	06/05/2025	Presentation of VIBES in the “ECO-AERO Day” event at PLATA’s facility.	Industry Scientific Community	Spain

3.8 Layman’s Report

The Layman’s report was produced as a final report of the VIBES project, summarising the work of the project for a general audience. It serves as a valuable marketing tool for promoting the environmental and economic benefits of the project results and extending the impact of the project beyond the area of implementation. It clearly outlines the achievements of the project and its long-term environmental and economic benefits to attract the interest of journalists and policymakers, along with experts and stakeholders focusing on similar issues to those addressed by the project.

The Layman’s report includes the following information:

- The problem, introducing one or two paragraphs on the background to the project.
- Project overview, introducing the project’s specific objectives, the partners involved, as well as the project duration and budget.
- Results, introducing the innovative solutions in a non-technical way, describing the innovative solutions brought to the market thanks to the project.
- The market, introducing the target users and customers.
- The benefits of the innovative solutions (environmental, cost-benefit).
- The European added value, introducing the benefits at EU level.
- Contact information, including e-mail and website.

The Layman’s report is 16 pages in length, including cover, contents and end pages, produced in both electronic and printable formats. It has been presented in an attractive way, using eye-catching images where possible and presenting results in an easy-to-read way, such as tables, charts, and boxes. The Layman’s report can be viewed and downloaded from the [promotional material](#) section of the project’s website and from Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15279451>). A [short video](#) is also available on the project’s YouTube channel, introducing the VIBES Layman’s report.

3.9 Internal Communication

Daily communication between partners has been achieved through email. Exchange of detailed information between Work Packages has also been through email and by meetings.

To facilitate communication, the following emailing lists have been established.

Table 8. Internal mailing lists

LIST	MEMBERS
vibes_all@vibesproject.eu	It includes every participating member of VIBES consortium
vibes_technical@vibesproject.eu	It includes every member of VIBES consortium who is responsible for technical issues

LIST	MEMBERS
vibes_administration@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for administrative issues
vibes_dissemination@vibesproject.eu	It includes all members of VIBES consortium who are responsible for the dissemination of the project

4. Dissemination Means and Channels

Dissemination activities aimed at making the project results available to the scientific community, policy makers and industry, using scientific language and accurate statements.

4.1 Scientific Publications

It has been an obligation and of interest to the consortium to widely disseminate the proposed new materials and technologies through qualified scientific publications. Scientific publications and conferences have been important dissemination channels for sharing VIBES outcomes to academic and industrial target communities, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the results in their own. The academic and research partners have taken up the leading role in drafting scientific articles, assisted by all relevant consortium members. At least 6 scientific publications have been planned, including at least 4 articles in scientific journals and at least 2 posters in scientific conferences. The targets have been reached and surpassed.

In particular, VIBES partners participated in publishing the following peer-reviewed scientific articles, relevant to the VIBES approach and technological developments.

University of Limerick:

- Maurice N. Collins, Mario Culebras, Guang Ren, “Chapter 8 - The use of lignin as a precursor for carbon fiber-reinforced composites”, peer-reviewed chapter in the book with the title “Micro and Nanolignin in Aqueous Dispersions and Polymers: Interactions, Properties, and Applications”, published by Elsevier, 2022, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823702-1.00011-6>
- Rubio, M.C., Beaucamp, A., Stróżyk, M.A., Collins, M.N. (2022), “Lignin-based carbon fibers for high-performance Green Composites”, *Encyclopedia of Green Materials*, pp. 1–8, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4921-9_155-1
- Beaucamp, A. et al. (2022), “Lignin for Energy Applications – State of the art, life cycle, technoeconomic analysis and future trends”, *Green Chemistry*, 2022, 24, pp. 8193–8226, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2GC02724K>
- Stróżyk, M.A. et al. (2024), “Decreasing the environmental impact of carbon fibre production via microwave carbonisation enabled by self-assembled nanostructured coatings”, *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials*, 7(2), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-024-00853-2>
- Muhammad Muddasar, Anne Beaucamp, Mark Vaughan, Misbah Mushtaq, Mario Culebras, Marina M. Leite, Tadhg Kennedy, Maurice N. Collins, “Chapter 14 - Carbon (Nano)Fibers and Carbon Materials from Lignin and Their Applications”, peer-reviewed chapter in the book with the title

“Lignin Chemistry: Characterization, Isolation, and Valorization”, published by Wiley, 2024, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527839865.ch14>

- Caitriona Winters, Marta Carsi, Maria J. Sanchis, Mario Culebras, Maurice N. Collins (2024), “On the design of lignin reinforced acrylic acid/hyaluronic acid adhesive hydrogels with conductive PEDOT:HA nanoparticles”, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 273, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.133093>
- Caitriona Winters, Marta Carsi, Maria J. Sanchis, Mario Culebras, Maurice N. Collins (2024), “Electrically Conductive Lignin Reinforced Polyacrylic Acid/Hyaluronic Acid Scaffolds With PEDOT:HA Nanoparticles”, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies*, 35 (10), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.6607>
- Mark Vaughan, Anne Beaucamp, Maurice N. Collins (2025), “Development of high stiffness carbon fibres from lignin”, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 292, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2024.112024>

AITIIP, LEITAT, University of Limerick:

- Vidal, J. et al. (2023), “Use of covalent dynamic networks as binders on epoxy-based carbon fiber composites: Effect on properties, processing, and recyclability”, *Polymer Composites*, 44(11), pp. 7444–7456, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.27636>

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4.2 Participation in Scientific Conferences

Participating in scientific conferences is a unique opportunity to reach audiences with various scientific and industrial backgrounds that are relevant to VIBES. Throughout the duration of the VIBES project, partners planned to participate in at least 3 scientific conferences, in which VIBES approach, methodologies and results would be presented to relevant international scientific forums.

The consortium partners participated in 37 scientific conferences and forums, presenting VIBES approach and methodologies. The total target of participation in scientific conferences has been reached and

surpassed. The following table lists the scientific conferences and related events, in which partners participated, presenting VIBES.

Table 9. Presentation of VIBES approach at scientific conferences & events

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
ULIM	22/07/2021	Online presentation: “An abundant resource of biocarbon for advanced engineering applications” of the project at the International Conference on Resource Sustainability (icRS 2021)	Scientific community	International
DITF	15/09/2021	Presentation at Dornbirn GFC digital conference on “Low-cost carbon fibres: High-molecular weight Lignin combined with Low-Pressure Stabilization Technology”.	Industry	International
ULIM	15/09/2021	Presentation at a network seminar (virtual), organised by the University of Bristol/ Catapult UK, on “Sustainable Composite materials for Wind Turbine Blades; Development of Lignin Fibres for Energy”	Industry	UK
BCIRC	14/10/2021	“Innovative and sustainable solutions for the nautic sector” presentation at the “INTERNATIONAL NAUTICTECH FORUM” conference.	Industry	Spain
DITF	09/11/2021	Presentation at the “Aachen-Dresden-Denkendorf International Textile - ADDITC” on “Stabilisation of polyacrylonitrile precursors by low-pressure technology for low-cost carbon fibres” presentation.	Industry	International

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
ULIM	21/10/2021	Online presentation on “Lignin - An abundant bioresource for next generation sustainable advanced engineering composites, at the Institute of Materials Mining and Minerals (IOM3) International Conference on Manufacturing (ICMAC).	Scientific community	International
PLATA	29/11/2021	Presentation at “Instituto Ingeniería de España” conference.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	02/02/2022	Reference to the VIBES innovation in the presentation of Mandala project at the “The European Biopolymer Summit 2022”.	Scientific community	Europe
AITIIP	02/03/2021	Participation to “Webinar IA2” with the presentation “Cómo innovar en nuevos modelos de economía circular y envases/materiales más sostenibles”.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	17/02/2022	Participation to the scientific seminar of the International University Menéndez Pelayo and Polymers Institute with the presentation titled "Solid state polymers"	Scientific community	Spain
PLATA	03/03/2022	Presentation at "Desarrollo e innovación en Aeropuerto Internacional de Teruel" conference.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	23/03/2022	Online participation at the “S3 - 4th European Eco-plasturgy	Scientific community	Europe

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		Congress” with a presentation on Thermosets towards a circular economy: sustainable recycling technologies.		
AITIIP	06/04/2022	Poster’s exhibition at the 11th R&D European Framework Conference aiming to analyse the first year of the Horizon Europe Programme and the Spanish participation.	Industry	Spain
BCIRC	13/10/2022	Participation to the “Sustainability in Composites challenges and opportunities”.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	26/10/2022	Presentation of VIBES to technical audience in the 2022 edition of EMPACK within the Mandala’s project Final Conference.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	14 - 16/11/2022	Presentation of VIBES at the European Summit of Industrial Biotechnology 2022 (ESIB 2022).	Industry	Europe
ULIM	8/03/2023	Participation to the SAMPE conference with “ Production of Lignin-based Carbon Fibers” presentation.	Scientific Community	Northern Ireland
AITIIP	21-23/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the industrial audience of the “eMobility Expo & World Congress”.	Industry	Spain
AITIIP	27-31/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the “Wake Up Spain” Forum.	Industry, Scientific community, policymakers	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
AITIIP	28/03/2023	Presentation of VIBES to the industrial audience of the “Excellence Forum Automotive Cluster”.	Industry	Europe
SP	23-27/04/2023	Participation of VIBES at the “APME : 14th Advanced Polymers via Macromolecular Engineering”.	Scientific Community	France
AITIIP	04/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the “ECP4 sustainable composites” conference.	Technical	Spain
SP	14-18/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES with a scientific poster at the EUPOC.	Scientific Community	Europe
PLATA	15/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the “Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya” conference.	Scientific Community	Spain
F&D	20/05/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the 4th International Conference on biobased and biodegradable textiles and polymers.	Scientific community	Europe
PLATA	14-15/07/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Antonio Gargallo University Foundation’s conference for advances and development of the aeronautical and aerospace sector.	Scientific Community	Spain
LEITAT	13/09/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Global Fiber Congress.	Scientific Community	Europe
AITIIP	21/09/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the “Ippt-twin 1 International” conference.	Technical	Slovenia
AITIIP	23/10/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the	Technical	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		“Polymer Connect” conference.		
AITIIP	31/10/2023	Presentation of VIBES at the Packnet conference: "Circular innovation in packaging: the road to a sustainable future."	Technical	Spain
AITIIP	23/11/2023	Participation to the Quality Innovation Awards 2023, winning the “Innovation in Circular Economy and Zero Carbon Footprint” prize and presenting the VIBES lines of research.	Scientific community	Spain
AITIIP	13/02/2024	Participation to the “eMobility Expo World Congress” with the VIBES presentation “New materials for the new vehicles”.	Industry	Spain
ULIM	30/04/2024	Presentation of VIBES project “Future opportunities for Lignin derived Advanced Materials” at the NOMATEN centre of excellence in multifunctional materials for industrial and medical applications.	Scientific community	Poland
PLATA	06/05/2024	Presentation of VIBES at the Teruel International Airport conference related to its development and innovation.	Scientific community	Spain
PLATA	12-13/07/2024	Participation to the Antonio Gargallo University Foundation conference on “Advances and development of the aeronautical and aerospace sector”, with a presentation on “Innovation, sustainability and challenges in the aeronautical and aerospace	Scientific community	Spain

Partner	Date	Type of event/ Description	Type of audience	Countries addressed
		industry”.		
ULIM	09/04/2025	Participation to the “International Conference on Manufacturing of Advanced Composites 2025” (ICMAC 2025), with a presentation titled “Towards sustainable CF, precursor, processing and characterisation”.	Scientific community	International
LEITAT	04-07/05/2025	Participation to the “15th Advanced Polymers via Macromolecular Engineering” Conference (APME25), with a scientific poster on “Exploring a Bio-Based Bonding Material (BBM) for improved recyclability of thermoset composites”.	Scientific community	Italy

4.3 Organisation of Events

In the frame of VIBES, several events have been organised to serve the project’s objectives and promote the project and its outcomes. In more detail, the following types of events were organised, as part of the project’s dissemination plan.

4.3.1 COMPOSIFORUM International Events

COMPOSIFORUM is the “Composites Forum for the Industry and Researchers”, organised by AITIIP in collaboration with the University of Zaragoza, as part of the AITIIP Chair (AITIIP CATEDRA) that advises and defines the strategic lines of Research, Development and Innovation projects of mutual interest between the University of Zaragoza and AITIIP foundation.

COMPOSIFORUM gathers experts in plastic composites and takes place every two years. The 2022 edition took place in Zaragoza on 17th November 2022 and focused on sustainability and circularity as strategic axes of the new economy. Prestigious speakers from the science and industrial arena participated. A lecture slot was reserved specifically for the dissemination of the VIBES project in 2022.

Due to an internal decision at the organisational level of AITIIP, it was determined that the 2024 edition of COMPOSIFORUM would not take place. However, as mentioned in section 4.3.2., AITIIP exploited other opportunities for organising workshops to disseminate VIBES approach and results, even though they were not initially planned.

4.3.2 Demonstration and other Workshops

The organisation of three (3) demonstration workshops took place as planned, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept. The following three (3) demonstration workshops were organised.

A 5-hour workshop was organised together with HELACS project and focused on dismantling, collecting, sorting and directing processes and composites waste manipulation. This workshop took place on 29th July, 2021 at PLATA premises in Teruel (Spain) with the participation of Airbus, PLATA and AITIIP. There were 12 participants (33% female) from the aeronautic sector, technology providers, dismantling and recycling companies. During the workshop different aspects of VIBES and HELACS, advanced materials, efficient manufacturing, circular economy and digitalisation were treated with the aim of gathering feedback and engagement. The event allowed us to confirm that the objectives of VIBES are aligned to industry and stakeholders. They are interested in the results and think that they will be useful in their future processes. They also expressed their intention to participate actively in project activities and future initiatives.

Figure 18. Demonstration workshop in Teruel

A 2-hour workshop was organised together with BIZENTE, polynSPIRE and LIFE RECYSITE projects on dealing with properties, industrial applications and end-of-life alternatives of thermoset composites. This workshop took place on 2nd July, 2021 at CIRCE premises in Zaragoza (Spain) with the aim of establishing synergies and interactions with pPolynSPIRE project. There were 6 participants (20% female) from research and innovation centres. The workshop included a technical discussion about polyamide degradation processes and a visit to the lab in which the microwave solvolysis processes take place, which served as feedback for the green solvolysis process developed in VIBES. The event allowed us to confirm the alignment of the VIBES objectives to current research lines and the interest of the scientific community in its results.

Figure 19. Demonstration workshop in Zaragoza

A 3-hour workshop, titled “Biobased Thermoset Composites for Advanced Engineering Applications”, was combined with the project’s Final Conference on “Advancing Green Recycling for Thermoset Composites” (see section 4.3.4). This workshop, organised as a hybrid event in Barcelona (Spain) on 8th May 2025, put on the spotlight the transformative role of VIBES innovations in key sectors such as aeronautics, construction, and naval engineering. There were 59 participants (50% female), 20 on-site and 39 online, representing academia & research, technology & innovation, industry and policy. Key industrial partners of the project consortium presented real-world applications that highlight the growing impact of biobased thermoset composites in engineering. A coffee and networking session offered attendees the chance to connect and exchange ideas in a relaxed setting. The workshop concluded with a thought-provoking expert panel discussion, including invited members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board. The panel discussion focused on the barriers and opportunities in adopting green recycling technologies, including critical policy aspects such as Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). Whether joining in person or online, participants gained insights into cutting-edge solutions and collaborative paths forward for sustainable industrial transformation.

Figure 20. Demonstration workshop in Barcelona

In addition to the above planned demonstration workshops, five more workshops were organised, as part of other relevant activities, in which the VIBES project was presented:

- A workshop organised by AITIIP on 22/3/2022, in Zaragoza (Spain), in which VIBES was presented as part of a training course related to moulding and plastic injection and circular economy, addressed to industry.
- A workshop organised by AITIIP, with the participation of speakers from AITIIP and LEITAT, on 18/5/2022, in Capri (Italy) at the SUM Symposium, with the title “[Sustainability of thermoset materials](#)”, addressed to the scientific community and exposing the different approaches that are being followed for the treatment of thermosets, including the VIBES approach.
- On 02/12/2022, the University of Limerick hosted a workshop for secondary school students, highlighting the research conducted on lignin as part of the VIBES project.
- On 28/2/2024, AITIIP organised an additional demonstration workshop at PLATA facilities in Teruel (Spain), addressed to industry.
- On 10/4/2025, AITIIP organised a workshop for primary school students, presenting the achievements of the VIBES project.

Figure 21. Additional demonstration workshop at PLATA facilities in Teruel

Figure 22. Workshop for primary school students in ATIIP

4.3.3 Roundtables

In addition to the workshops mentioned above, two roundtables were planned by Q-PLAN as part of the VIBES Stakeholders Board activities. The roundtables were organised at key turning points of the VIBES project, hosting the VIBES Stakeholders Board with the participation of project partners, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy. The social changes and impact that VIBES may have in the society were also explored.

The first roundtable event was held on November 29th, 2023 in a hybrid format at Disini Hotel, Montpellier (France), and online via MS Teams, bringing together crucial stakeholders and members of the VIBES Stakeholders' Board. Q-PLAN organised the event in detail, ensuring meticulous planning from tailored invitations to the distribution of pre-event materials. A total of 20 attendees (55% female), including 6 Stakeholders' Board members, actively participated in the discussions.

The overarching goal of the roundtable was to gather insights from external stakeholders, fostering a productive dialogue aimed at maximising the impact of project actions. Moderated by Q-PLAN, the event delved into key aspects of the project, particularly focusing on the design approaches of thermoset composites with intrinsic recyclability and their scale-up steps. These approaches encompassed biobased components, such as biobased bonding materials (BBMs), resins, and fibres. Expert presentations by leaders of Work Packages 1, 2 and 3 highlighted crucial milestones.

The interactive discussions explored the properties of innovative biobased materials, developed by the project, in relation to market needs and challenges for scaling up. Noteworthy topics included cost and supply chain dynamics, scalability issues, and the intricate nature of biobased materials.

Figure 23. VIBES first roundtable in Montpellier

The second roundtable event was held on November 14th, 2024, in a hybrid format at AITIIP’s headquarters in Zaragoza (Spain), and online via MS Teams, bringing together again key stakeholders, members of the VIBES Stakeholders’ Board. Moderated by Q-PLAN, the event demonstrated planning, from invitations to pre-event materials distribution, ensuring the active participation of 27 attendees (51% female), including 6 members of the Stakeholders’ Board.

The goal of the event was to gather insights from external stakeholders by stimulating a concrete discussion, aiming to leverage the effort of the project's actions towards successful results. The event's structure featured insightful presentations of design approaches of thermoset composites with intrinsic recyclability and their scale-up steps, focusing on their biobased components including biobased bonding materials (BBMs), resins and fibres, considering also the approaches for their recycling capabilities. The presentations also included the upscaling of the best components for thermoset multilayer fibrous composites, the design and development of inherently recyclable thermoset composites, and their technical validation in three sectors (aeronautics, construction, and naval). The VIBES updates ended with the debonding and separation of recyclable thermoset components and the valorisation and upcycling of recovered thermoset composite components.

Key discussions included scaling up biobased resin production, pilot testing recyclable materials, and addressing fibre and resin compatibility challenges, with discussions focusing on technical hurdles such as water absorption, fibre strength, and cost barriers. Recycling technologies and processes, including composite waste management and pilot plant development, were also discussed, emphasising innovations like biobased solvents and effective material recovery strategies.

During the second roundtable, the commercialisation of solutions through tailored business models and market readiness strategies was also addressed, while feedback underscored the need for precursor optimisation, thermomechanical performance, and cost reduction to ensure market adoption. The

roundtable reinforced the importance of aligning these advancements with regulatory developments and fostering a circular economy in industries like aeronautics, construction, and naval sectors.

Figure 24. VIBES second roundtable in Zaragoza

The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN) collected feedback from the participation of Stakeholders’ Board members in the two roundtables and in the panel discussion of the final demonstration workshop (see section 4.3.2.) and presented them in the deliverable D6.6 “Feedback on key points from stakeholders’ panel activities” on month 48.

4.3.4 Final Conference

The final conference of the VIBES project took place on 8th May 2025, in a hybrid format in Barcelona, Spain, attracting an audience of 59 stakeholders (50% female) from academia, industry, and policy. The event served as a platform to highlight and disseminate the project’s key achievements in developing sustainable solutions for thermoset composite recycling.

The event was organised by the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN), in collaboration with the Project Coordinator (AITIIP), and supported by local partners LEITAT and BCIRCULAR that assisted in identifying and selecting appropriate facilities. All project partners contributed to the success of the event by promoting it through their networks—reaching out to suppliers, clients, and collaborators—primarily from academic and industrial backgrounds. Key stakeholders were invited to participate, including two distinguished keynote speakers and members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

The conference commenced with opening remarks from Marta Redrado Notivoli, VIBES Project Coordinator (AITIIP), followed by a welcome address from Chloe Johnson, Project Officer from the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE-JU), the project's funding authority under Horizon 2020. Her address emphasised the strategic role of sustainable materials innovation within the EU research and innovation landscape.

Dr José Sánchez Gomez, Composites Expert at the Spanish Association of Composite Materials (AEMAC), delivered an insightful keynote titled *"Composite Airframe Applications, Lessons Learnt and New Challenges"*. His presentation outlined technical advances and future opportunities for composites in aerospace applications.

In a dedicated session, Dr Julio Vidal (AITIIP) presented the core technological breakthroughs achieved within the VIBES project, including:

- Development of biobased epoxy resins and fibres
- Creation of thermoset composites with intrinsic recyclability
- Deployment of green chemical recycling methods

Ms Mona Jesri, Head of Sustainable Polymers and Composites at the Advanced Manufacturing Innovation Centre (AMIC), Northern Ireland, delivered the second keynote on *"Circular Natural Fibre Composites: Innovations, Challenges, and Path to Wider Industry Adoption"*. She addressed both the latest materials innovations and the challenges of scaling these solutions for wider industrial application.

To complement the technical presentations, Francesca Braca (ARCHA) provided an overview of the regulatory framework influencing the adoption of sustainable composite materials, highlighting its impact on both product development and market entry strategies.

Throughout the day, attendees engaged in interactive discussions and networking. The conference effectively showcased VIBES contribution to the circular economy and reaffirmed its impact on shaping the future of sustainable composite manufacturing in Europe.

Figure 25. VIBES final conference in Barcelona

5. Training Programme

A training programme was aligned with the communication and dissemination strategy with the aim of providing knowledge and skills to potential industrial collaborators and stakeholders of the VIBES project and to science and engineering students. The Training programme in the project represents the strategic vision of the Consortium in view of sharing and therefore implementing the open knowledge that has been gathered and generated within the project, both by the science students and by professionals in varied industrial sectors.

The training activities also contribute to the dissemination and therefore exploitation of the project results, contributing to raising awareness and providing novel competencies in the current and next generation of professionals.

The Project Coordinator (AITIIP) was responsible for designing, planning and organising the training programme, producing the deliverable D7.6 “Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals”.

5.1 Training strategy

Training activities contribute to professional development, through advanced training of researchers and other key staff, science students, industry staff, and in general potential users of the knowledge generated by the project.

The complementary expertise of the partners within the project have a positive effect in generating cross-collaboration, a better capacity for training of young researchers and eventually fruitful staff exchange (e.g. between academia and enterprises).

The specific targets of the training activities are:

- **transfer** of knowledge within the participants including students, researchers and industrial staff.
- **spreading** of knowledge from both the academic and industrial professional within the project to researchers and students and to industrial staff outside the consortium, promoting S&T cohesion within the European research goals and so increase skills across Europe
- raising **awareness** of key stakeholders who are essential to successful exploitation and commercialization of the novel technology and products developed.

The approach used in the project is based on Open Science, focused on open dissemination and open materials.

It is generally accepted that Open Science leads to increased impact associated with wider sharing and re-use and could increase trust in science and in the reliability of scientific results.

In 2014, a core set of principles were drafted in order to optimise the reusability of research data, named the FAIR Data Principles. They represent a community-developed set of guidelines and best practices to ensure that data or any digital object are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable. This concept was used in VIBES in training design:

- **Findable:** The first thing to be in place to make data reusable is the possibility to find them. In VIBES cases, the training is available through an e-learning platform (aitemy learning)
- **Accessible:** The data can be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised and open protocol that guarantee a simple access. In this sense, the e-learning platform used, is intuitive and user-friendly.
- **Interoperable:** The data can be combined with and used with other data or tools.
- **Re-usable:** Ultimately, FAIR aims at optimizing the reuse of data. In this sense, VIBES created OERs (Open Education Resources) that could be used by other teachers and learners.

5.2 Objectives, Target Audiences and Themes

The training programme was designed and implemented with the aim of providing knowledge and skills on the topic of new recycling technologies for composite materials and the circular economy as well as to present and transfer the knowledge and results acquired during the project.

The training programme was promoted among the VIBES stakeholders that are included in the VIBES stakeholders’ database as well as Universities and Education Centres and other relevant contacts of the consortium partners. The stakeholders’ database was created by sharing relevant contacts and information among project partners using the “Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders” form (see Annex 1).

In particular, the training programme focused on the following types of stakeholders:

- Researchers from academia and technicians related to VIBES interconnected sectors (materials science, chemistry, chemical engineering, biotechnology, recycling and waste management)
- Industrial professionals who may potentially collaborate with and/ or be involved in the business that VIBES key exploitable results will generate (industrial developers, converters, dismantlers, waste managers and end-users).
- Science and engineering students (fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry), with the aim of creating a breeding ground of new talent for the creation of future jobs aligned with the new social and industrial needs.
- Anyone in the open society who is interested in the subject of green technologies and circular economy.

VIBES training is focused on some specific themes:

- Design and development of biobased materials
- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

VIBES validates a better use of resources demonstrating the high potential of the Circular Economy to implement a resilient energy union with forward-looking climate change policies. This validation is based on a technology evolution through scientific excellence (a first cost-effective recycling technology based on the development of smart BBM for the first time applied to composite thermoset plastic) which will equip to Chemical Industry to make Europe a stronger global actor and will this knowledge to design and implement the training activities.

5.3 Training Methodology

The training activities were held in a variety of formats and methods, both in presence - workshops, technological breakfast and face to face courses - and remotely - online training. Certificates of attendance are envisaged for all the training sessions, both online and in presence after completing a test.

5.3.1 Face to face training sessions

Venues for the training events were selected carefully and minimum requirements were the availability of hardware (projectors/wide screens) and internet connection that allowed for interactive activities to engage the audience and of course to guarantee the necessary security of the audience (COVID pandemic is an example).

The training events have been organised in Spain and Ireland; to increase the engagement, local language is highly recommended for the national events.

Events occurring in presence allow for higher involvement of the audience and longer sessions of training that may deepen the participants' knowledge on specific topics addressed by the event.

5.3.2 Online training sessions

The advantage of online training is the wider coverage and the possibility to re-play and learn following a personal path and rhythm. Remote sessions however are usually less interactive and do not allow for a profound discussion of the thematic covered by the event.

In this case, the online training will be an e-learning course and a recording of the summer course. It is available to the public on **aitemy learning platform** (<https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>) and though a link on VIBES website.

The online learning content allow trainees to undertake the course at their own convenience. Course material is offered via recorded video and presentation slides. Upon completion of the course, AITIIP can release certificates to those who passed the requirements.

A link was integrated with the VIBES website, allowing it to further become the single point of reference for VIBES trainees.

5.3.3 Evaluation

The course includes formative assessment. There are different types of exercises and can be automatically checked. There is also a questionnaire in the face-to face event to value the trainees satisfaction.

5.4 Training activities

The training is being articulated around the following channels.

1. Research workshops for researchers and technicians.
2. Summer course for students, replicated at the University of Limerick summer school.
3. Free access to training material, generated by the summer course, through AITIIP e-learning platform (aitemy), open for both students and society.
4. Technological breakfast and workshops at AITIIP facilities for industrial professionals.

In each course or workshop special care will be taken so that there is a gender equality among participants, a balance between male and female participants.

5.4.1 Research Workshops for researchers and technicians

Three research-oriented workshops were organised for researchers and technicians, gathering researchers from academia and industry related to VIBES interconnected sectors.

These workshops focused on researchers and technicians’ profiles mainly coming from Spain and Ireland. The three workshops were organised following key milestones of the project, with the aim of transferring knowledge and gather feedback from peers.

- On 17/12/2024, AITIIP organised a workshop on Circular Economy, providing a training session at AITIIP facilities (22 attendees).

Figure 26. Workshop about Circular Economy at AITIIP

- On 05/02/2025, AITIIP provided a training workshop about composites at the University of Limerick, especially focusing on VIBES results (16 attendees).

Figure 27. Workshop at University of Limerick

- On 13/02/2025, AITIIP provided a training workshop about VIBES results at the University of Zaragoza (15 attendees).

Figure 28. Workshop at University of Zaragoza

5.4.2 Summer Training Course

The training for students is oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It will include a summer course, covering 30 hours of training. The course curriculum includes latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project. The VIBES consortium partners prepare the content of the training. The training was launched in May 2023. Twenty-four (24) hours were developed as an e-learning course, with a final face to face Summer Course in PLATA.

The contents of the course were:

- Design and development of biobased materials
- Practical applications in industry
- Green technologies to recycle/reuse components.

The following contents has been developed:

Module 1: Design and development of strategies to include thermoset plastics into circular economy (10 hours)

Explanation: development of CANs and biobased resins

- CANs general approach what are these materials → 1.5 Hour
- Supramolecular approach → 2 Hours
- Vitrimer approach → 2 Hours
- D-A approach → 2 hours

- Synthesis of bio resins → 1.5 Hour
- Use of green solvents → 1 Hour

Module 2: Biobased and improved fibres a key for the success of a composite (8 hours)

Explanation: manufacture and modify the structure and chemical properties of the textile reinforcements used in composite materials

- Linseed material: Possible configurations and potential → 1.5 Hour
- Carbon fibre and chemical modification of its surface to boost its properties and allow recyclability → 2.5 Hours
- Fabrication of biobased CF & Sizings development → 2.5 Hours
- Scaling up and fabrication of biobased CF → 1.5 Hour

Module 3: Application of VIBES materials and technologies in the industry (6 hours)

Explanation: Within this module different sectors explain the interest, potential and applications that the developments of the project will have in their market

- Applications in the construction sector → 1.5 Hour
- Applications in the aeronautic sector → 1.5 Hour
- Applications in the naval industry → 1.5 Hour
- Potential of solvolysis in the industry of composites (B-circ) → 1.5 Hour

Module 4: Face-to-face summer course (6 hours)

- Composites, recycling techniques and their market impact.
- Use of enzymes as a method of recycling composites.
- Covalent networks in thermoset composite.
- Cutting of composite parts for better dismantling and recycling.
- Redesign of materials to include in a circular economy - Reinforcement and matrix.
- Visit to the facilities.

Under the coordination of AITIIP, the partners collaborated in the creation of the contents from 18th month of the project. The practical session was done in PLATA facilities on 15th September 2023 during around 6 hours. 16 persons participated directly and one through online connection. An evaluation was done at the end of the course.

The summer course was organised in Teruel Campus, a rural area in south Aragon region that belongs to the University of Zaragoza and located next to PLATA facilities which was visited in order to familiarise future employees with the industry environment of vision, problem identification and solution implementation from the circular economy perspective.

The summer course, organised jointly with "Antonio Gargallo" University Foundation, aims to promote cooperation between the University of Zaragoza, the Public Administrations of the Autonomous

Community of Aragon and the institutions and socio-economic agents of the province of Teruel for the development of the University Campus of Teruel, by carrying out actions and setting up its own projects or those agreed with companies or public and private institutions.

The Summer University of Teruel (UVT) is a programme of activities of the "Antonio Gargallo" University Foundation, consisting of a range of courses, seminars, workshops and scientific meetings held throughout the year, although preferably during the summer period.

The UVT is a substantial part of the summer activity of the University of Zaragoza, being this link compatible with a clear vocation of universality that also allows programming activities in collaboration with other universities or with other non-university bodies of recognised prestige, from the social and academic point of view; this is the case of certain training activities linked to public or private institutions. The offer is intended to be broad and plural, both in terms of topics and methodological approaches.

UVT advertised the course on its website: [Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials Through a Greener Recycling Technology | Fundación Universitaria Antonio Gargallo \(unizar.es\)](https://www.unizar.es/verano/2023/curso-teruel)

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials Through a Greener Recycling Technology

Ciencia y Tecnología Teruel

Fecha evento:
15/05/2023 to 15/09/2023

Director/Directores:
Dña. Eva Sanchis. Responsable de Formación. Socióloga con Máster en Técnicas Educativas Emergentes, en Gamificación y Narrativa Transmedia, en Comunidades Europeas y Unión Europea y en Investigación de Mercados.

Horas lectivas totales: 30

Precio de la matrícula:
Matrícula general: 20 euros.

[Matrícula](#)

Objetivos:

El alumno tendrá capacidad para gestionar la información procedente de diversas fuentes, valorando su relevancia, fiabilidad y pertinencia para un propósito determinado, analizándola y organizándola. Además facilitará al alumno el reconocimiento de los conceptos básicos sobre reciclabilidad de composites y su aplicación práctica a distintos sectores como construcción, aeronáutica o naval y su sensibilización en la importancia y repercusión de las tecnologías de reciclado de productos plásticos en particular y de la economía circular y sostenibilidad en general.

Objectives:

The student will have the ability to manage information from various sources, assessing its relevance, reliability, and relevance for a specific purpose, analyzing it and organizing it.

In addition, it will facilitate the student's recognition of the basic concepts on the recyclability of composites and their practical application to different sectors such as construction, aeronautics or naval and their awareness of the importance and impact of recycling technologies for plastic products in particular and for the circular economy and sustainability in general.

Programa:

The above Summer Course was replicated in the summer programme of the University of Limerick in May 2024.

Leading experts on composite materials gathered at the University of Limerick to discuss the future of composite materials and their key role in the transition to a biobased economic model. Lively discussion took place with distinguished members of the audience (online and in person) from both industry and academia.

The participation included 30 people in person and 25 online. Two LinkedIn posts about this training activity generated well over 5k impressions.

The agenda was the following:

- A quick fatigue assessment method for fibre reinforced composites. Dr Akshay Hejjaji (ULIM)
- Carbon Fibre production and life cycle assessment. Dr Anne Beaucamp (ULIM)
- New Resins, BBMs and Recycling. Dr Julio Vidal (AITIIP)
- Modelling and composite design Dr Giovanni Zucco (ULIM, School Of Engineering)
- Future CFRP products and commercial directions (Dr Saul Buchanan (JUNO Composites)
- Integrating Composites with Diverse Materials for Automotive and Aerospace Applications. Dr Kashif Bangash (ULIM)
- Latest techniques for composite manufacture. Dr Ronan O'Higgins (Head of School of Engineering, ULIM)
- Final comments Prof. Maurice N. Collins (ULIM)

The visit to PLATA facilities can be replicated by ACCIONA and IDEC in their own premises.

In both cases, the course was in English to facilitate its implementation in each facility and encourage the participation of other students from any EU member-state.

In parallel to the above training, AITIIP and the University of Limerick (ULIM) have extended the research results generated by the project by launching 3 PhD theses. In addition, 1 PhD thesis was launched by SPECIFIC POLYMERS as part of the project's research activities.

5.4.3 E-learning

As it is mentioned previously, to develop the Summer Course online content was created that complements the practical activities.

The e-learning includes a menu so that the trainees can choose if they prefer a linear learning or their own path.

It also includes speech and subtitles.

The interactive exercises allow the trainees to check their knowledge.

If their answer is wrong, the course informs the trainees, and they can decide if they continue or return to the exercise through the menu.

In order to ensure open access to the developed content and maximise the returns to society, the summer course was recorded. An open version for a wider student audience and the society in general has been uploaded and made free for use through AITIIP e-learning platform, aitemy: <https://aitemy-learning.com/gb/>, also shared in the [training section](#) of the project website.

The e-learning content was made available as soon as the summer courses in Teruel and Limerick took place.

The e-learning content is expected to reach at least 100 students and other stakeholders interested in the technological areas related to the VIBES project.

A certificate is handed to those having finalised the summer training course, described in section 5.4.2, and the open e-learning version of the VIBES training programme.

5.4.4 Training for Industrial Professionals

The training for industrial professionals was organised by AITIIP. The language of the events was Spanish due to the fact that all the events were located in the Aragonese region.

- **1st Technological breakfast:** On 23/11/2023 AITIIP organised a workshop titled “Course on recycling and waste treatment” presenting the VIBES project in AITIIP facilities (14 attendees).

Figure 29. 1st Technological breakfast

- On 15/03/2024, in collaboration with PLATA, AITIIP organised a workshop on Green Composites addressed to industry, in which AITIIP gave a lecture about VIBES within a training session in PLATA facilities (70 attendees).

Figure 30. Workshop in PLATA

- **2nd Technological breakfast.** To increase the impact, AITIIP decided to prepare a second Technological Breakfast. It was done on 28/11/2024 in AITIIP facilities (22 attendees).

Figure 31. 2nd Technological Breakfast

5.5 Training activities calendar

#	Date	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
1	M24	Online (AITEMY platform)	Course	E-learning contents for design and development of biobased materials, practical applications in industry and green technologies to recycle/reuse components.	Academia, industry, open society
2	M27	Spain	Course	Summer school course. The practical training for students was oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. It included the e-learning contents, until covering 30 hours of training.	Academia, industry, open society
3	M30	Spain	Workshop	1st Technological breakfast organised at AITIIP facilities for industrial professionals in the fields addressed by the VIBES project. The language of the event was Spanish.	Industry
4	M34	Spain	Workshop	Demonstration workshop for industry professionals organised at PLATA facilities.	Industry

#	Date	Venue	Format	Description	Audience
5	M36	Ireland	Course	Summer school course. The training for students was oriented towards undergraduate (first degree) or postgraduate (MSc) students in the fields of materials science, engineering and chemistry. The course curriculum included latest cutting-edge science and engineering topics in the main scientific and technological areas related to the VIBES project.	Academia, industry, open society
6	M42	Spain	Lecture/seminar	2nd Technological breakfast organised at AITIIP facilities for industrial professionals in the fields addressed by the VIBES project. The language of the event was Spanish.	Industry
7	M43	Spain	Workshop	A workshop for researchers and technicians was organised at AITIIP, explaining the VIBES project and its results. The duration was half day. The language of the workshop was Spanish.	Academia, industry
8	M45	Ireland	Workshop	A workshop for researchers and technicians was organised at the University of Limerick. The duration was half day. The language of the workshop was English.	Academia, industry
9	M45	Spain	Workshop	A workshop for researchers and technicians was organised by AITIIP at the University of Zaragoza, presenting VIBES achievements. The duration was half day. The language of the workshop was Spanish.	Academia, industry

6. Time Frame of Communication, Dissemination and Training activities

VIBES		Last updated: 28/4/2025																																																												
		2021												2022												2023												2024												2025												
		Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	
WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Training		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48													
T6.1-Development of the communication, dissemination, and training plan																																																														
Reporting on communication, dissemination and training activities																																																														
Achieving communication and dissemination KPIs																																																														
T6.2- Communication activities																																																														
Setting up a Stakeholders database and contact list																																																														
Design of project logo and visual identity																																																														
Design of project leaflets																																																														
Design of infographic																																																														
Production of promotional videos																																																														
Design of document and presentation templates																																																														
Image galleries																																																														
Project website development and reporting/ regular updates																																																														
Social Media accounts launch/ regular posts																																																														
e-Newsletters																																																														
Press releases																																																														
Participation in radio or TV programmes																																																														
Articles in press and industry magazines																																																														
Participation in events/ fairs/ info-days																																																														

VIBES Last updated: 28/4/2025		2021												2022												2023												2024												2025				
		Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May					
		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48					
WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Training																																																						
T6.3- Dissemination activities																																																						
Scientific publications																																																						
Participation in scientific conferences																																																						
COMPOSIFORUM international events																																																						
Demonstration workshops																																																						
Other workshops																																																						
Roundtables																																																						
Final Conference																																																						
Feedback on key points from stakeholders' panel activities																																																						
T6.4- Training activities																																																						
Research workshops																																																						
Summer training course																																																						
E-learning																																																						
Training for industrial professionals																																																						
Detailed content of VIBES skills for training: students & professionals																																																						

7. Performance Indicators, Monitoring and Reporting

7.1 Performance Indicators and Monitoring

The implementation of communication and dissemination strategy was monitored on an on-going basis according to the level of realisation of the communication and dissemination objectives and outcomes that were set up. The frequent evaluation of communication and dissemination activities allowed to monitor and measure their impact and, if necessary, adapt them in order to increase the project’s visibility and awareness. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager had the overall responsibility of the monitoring and evaluation of VIBES communication and dissemination activities, although the project partners were also expected to help by continuously monitoring and evaluating the publicity and communication activities they carried out.

Analytical measures and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were used in order to monitor the implementation and assess the impact of communication, dissemination and training activities. A number of metrics employed for the monitoring and evaluation of these activities are provided in the following Table, together with their target values. Beside the quantitative metrics indicated below, qualitative data were also gathered by eliciting feedback from stakeholders, on all occasions that allowed direct contact with them (e.g. roundtables, final event & workshop), and reported in the deliverable “D6.6 Feedback on key points from stakeholders’ panel activities”.

Table 10. KPIs and target values

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
Number of Stakeholders Board Members	At least 10 (at least 30% female)	13 (46 % female)			
Number of pieces of news posted on VIBES website	N/A	56	Number of visits to the VIBES website	15,000 unique visitors by the end of the project (indicative)	12,000

¹ The essential KPIs for monitoring the implementation of the communication, dissemination and training activities are marked in bold; they are those with target values that are specific and not indicative (specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement). The rest of the KPIs are for assessing the impact of the communication, dissemination and training activities; they are considered as equally important, but their target values are indicative (unless they are specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement).

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
Number of posts on VIBES social media accounts	N/A	254 (Twitter/X) 254 (LinkedIn) 254 (Facebook)	Number of followers in the VIBES social media accounts	2,000 followers (indicative) (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube)	360 (Twitter/X) 802 (LinkedIn) 200 (Facebook) 18 (YouTube)
Number of project leaflets designed	2 (one in the beginning and one at the mid-end)	2	Number of distributed promotional materials	2,000 copies of leaflets distributed in project/external events (indicative)	1100
Number of project infographics designed	1	1			
Number of project videos produced	2 (one in the beginning and one at the end)	2	Number of project video viewers	500 (indicative)	610
Number of e-newsletters	8 (2 per year, covering the activities developed every semester)	8	Number of subscribers to e-newsletters	500 (indicative)	396
Number of press	At least 6	9	Number of press	N/A	19

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
releases (in English)			release publications in local media		
			Number of citizens reached via media publications (press releases)	N/A	16,980
Number of radio or TV programmes that VIBES was communicated to	2	3			
Number of articles published in industry magazines	At least 4	4	Number of industrial stakeholders reached via media publications (industry magazines)	1,500	4,620
Number of events /fairs/ info-days in which partners participated presenting VIBES	At least 6	39	Number of stakeholders (industry) reached via VIBES participation in exhibitions and trade fairs		
			Number of participants (industrial stakeholders & policy makers) in events in which partners presented VIBES	500	1,300

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
Number of scientific papers published	At least 6 (at least 4 articles in scientific journals and 2 posters in conferences)	13 (articles in scientific journals) 3 (posters in scientific conferences)			
Number of scientific conferences in which partners participated presenting VIBES	At least 3	37	Number of participants (scientific community & industry) in scientific conferences in which partners presented VIBES	3,000	4,712
Number of COMPOSIFORUM international events organised	At least 2	1	Number of participants in COMPOSIFORUM international events	100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	80
Number of demonstration workshops organised for industry and stakeholders	3	3	Number of participants in the demonstration workshops	50 participants in total (indicative) (at least 30% female – indicative)	77
Number of other workshops organised	N/A	5	Number of participants in other organised workshops (industry & scientific community; primary & secondary school)	N/A	58 (industry & scientific community) 91

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
			students)		(primary & secondary school students)
Number of organised roundtables	2	2	Number of stakeholders that participated in roundtables	10 per roundtable	At least 20 participants per roundtable 6 stakeholders per roundtable
			Number of participants in the Final Conference	At least 100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	59
Number of summer training courses, organised as part of the training programme	2	2	Number of participants in the summer training courses	30 students per course (at least 30% female - indicative)	46 in total (onsite) 26 in total (online)
			Number of participants on e-learning platform: AITEMY	At least 100 participants (indicative) (at least 30% female - indicative)	
Number of research-oriented workshops organised for technicians and professionals	3	3	Number of professionals (academia and industry) participated in training (research-oriented,	At least 100 (indicative) (at least 30% female -	159

Achievement KPI ¹	Target Value	Current Status	Impact KPI	Target Value	Current Status
from academia and industry, as part of the training programme			technological breakfast, workshop)	indicative)	
Number of training activities for industrial professionals, organised as part of the training programme	2 (one technological breakfast and one workshop)	3 (two technological breakfasts and one demonstration workshop)			
Number of MSc theses launched	3	N/A			
Number of PhD theses launched	2	4			

The target of reaching 100,000 citizens refers to more than one communication KPIs, including number of citizens reached through project website visits, project social media, project video views, e-newsletters, published articles/press releases, as well as the consortium partners’ social media and other external digital channels. In total, it has been estimated from available data that at least **34,000 citizens** have been reached through communication activities. However, there are not enough data available, as reported by project partners’ activities, which can be used to correctly estimate the total figure of citizens reached.

Due to the lack of specific data for certain communication and dissemination activities, circulation data of media used for publications of articles and press releases as well as the number of visitors to exhibitions and trade fairs attended, provided an indication of the potential number of stakeholders reached. Based on this approach, relevant data indicate a **potential outreach** to at least **200,000 citizens** and **90,000 stakeholders from industry**.

In addition, certain strategic steps regarding online communication have been adjusted, trying to reach the corresponding targets:

- The number of VIBES social media posts has increased by posting twice per week in each social media account of the project; this approach has significantly increased the VIBES social media followers, in particular the LinkedIn followers.
- The e-newsletter subscribers have been linked to LinkedIn followers by publishing e-newsletters through VIBES LinkedIn account; this approach has had an immediate impact in significantly increasing the number of people that the e-newsletters reached.

- The VIBES social media posts have provided direct links to specific sections of the VIBES website with interesting content, such as news, video, training material, publications etc., attracting more visitors to the project website.
- Paid campaigns through X (Twitter) also attracted visitors to the project website. The first paid campaign started in October 2024 and ended in December 2024, resulting in a significant increase of new visitors to the project website. We therefore continued with a second paid campaign on X until the end of April 2025. Paid campaigns were also tried on LinkedIn but they did not result in any significant increase in the number of project website visitors.
- The communication with sister projects and other initiatives has been intensified, leading to an increase of reposts of our news and social media posts in their online channels, and vice versa; this approach has provided interesting material for our online channels while it has also had an immediate multiplier effect in reaching a wider audience.

It has been made evident that the number of unique visits to the VIBES website has significantly increased by following the above strategic steps. Furthermore, based on the available information, other communication and dissemination activities have proven to be quite effective in reaching and even exceeding the target values, such as publication of articles and press releases in local press and industry magazines and participation to events such as exhibitions and trade fairs.

7.2 Reporting

Communication and dissemination reporting was essential for keeping track of all the communication and dissemination activities that were carried out. Therefore, the project partners were expected to continuously report all their relevant activities on a six-months periodic report and to contribute to the continuous monitoring of VIBES communication and dissemination activities.

In order to facilitate the reporting of each communication and dissemination activity undertaken, four reporting tools were designed and shared with all partners, as shown in the following Table.

Table 11. Reporting tools for monitoring communication and dissemination activities

Annex	Reporting Tool	Coverage	When
11	Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template	All communication and dissemination activities, which partners were involved in during each project semester.	Every 6 months
12	News Reporting Template	News about project developments which partners were involved with.	Throughout the project
13	Event Reporting Form	Any event organised by the partners.	Within 30 days following the completion of the event

Annex	Reporting Tool	Coverage	When
14	External Conferences and Events Template	Any external conference/ event identified by partners, which was considered relevant to VIBES and beneficial to attend.	Throughout the project

7.2.1 Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

At the end of each project semester, all partners were expected to complete the “Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template” (Annex 10), reporting all communication and dissemination activities that they carried out in the corresponding semester.

This template is an Excel file that was completed by each partner at the end of each project semester and sent to Q-PLAN, providing all the required information. The European Commission collects all these data from the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (Q-PLAN). Therefore, for each activity each partner should indicate the following information:

- Partner name
- Date of activity (in order of occurrence / earlier first)
- Place of activity (online or physical location)
- Type of activity (selected from a drop-down list)
- Title of publication or event (if applicable)
- Title of article or presentation (if applicable)
- Type of audience (selected from a drop-down list)
- Size of audience (number of persons per type of audience)
- Language used / countries reached out
- Role and description of partner organisation’s involvement
- Type of project promotional material used (e.g. leaflets, infographic, project presentations)
- Quantity of project promotional material handed out (number of copies distributed per promotional material)
- Other partners or external organisations involved
- Short description of the activity
- Evidence: URL, screenshot, photo (given that the target group has given its consent)
- Significant contacts made (if relevant)
- Other comments (if relevant)

7.2.2 News Reporting Template

Partners were expected to share news about important project developments, including project approach, methodologies and results, organisation of events etc., by completing the “News Reporting Template” (Annex 11). The completed news reporting template should include the following information:

- News title
- News main content / description (a couple of paragraphs)

- Key words / hashtags (for social media)
- Relevant picture (if available)

The completed news reporting template should be sent to Q-PLAN, in order to communicate the corresponding news on the project’s website and social media.

7.2.3 Event Reporting Form

For each completed event (workshop, roundtable, final event etc.), partners were requested to complete the “Event Reporting Form” (Annex 12) providing information regarding the event that they were involved in. This form should be sent to Q-PLAN within 30 days after the end of the event and the event should also be communicated to Q-PLAN, in advance, for promotional purposes.

The event form is a structured document that should include the following information:

- Event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendees including % of female attendees, duration)
- Goals and relevance to the project
- Organisation of the event (if applicable)
- Dissemination activities within the event
- Structure of the event
- Outcomes of the event
- Evaluation of the event
- Annexes (list of participants, agenda, photos, presentations, if applicable)

7.2.4 External Conferences and Events Template

The “External Conferences and Events Template” is an Excel file (Annex 13), that partners could complete each time they identified an external event (e.g. conference, workshop, etc.) relevant to VIBES and in which VIBES partners might be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Each partner should share this file with Q-PLAN, which would then be communicated to all project partners.

For each identified external conference or any other relevant event, each partner should indicate the following information:

- Event Name
- Thematic Focus
- Date and Location
- Registration Fees
- Specific requirements for participation
- Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)
- Link to event website
- Name of partner

8. Conclusions

The current document constitutes the third and final updated version of the “Report on Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities” of the VIBES project. It has been developed by Q-PLAN, in collaboration with AITIP and input from all partners, under Work Package 6 “Communication, dissemination & training”.

With reference to the initial report elaborated in D6.2. and its first and second updates elaborated in D6.3 and D6.4, this report describes the objectives and the defined framework of project’s communication, dissemination and training strategy and provides a final update of the implemented communication, dissemination and training activities and corresponding channels, following the experience of the 48 months of the project implementation.

The project consortium has managed to create a consistent and recognisable visual identity and branding for the VIBES project and has made considerable efforts to reach out to the targeted stakeholder groups and relevant networks. Our communication, dissemination and training activities have been focused on raising awareness about the project’s approach and development, through the project online media, activities, synergies, contribution with new knowledge and through participation in relevant events.

Our latest efforts have been focused on deepening the connections made and networks built in local and EU context, to maximize the visibility and outreach of VIBES. To this end, all partners have kept on actively contributing to the communication and dissemination activities through the exploitation of the defined dissemination tools and channels, promoting and multiplying publicity of the project’s aims and achievements and disseminating targeted messages to all relevant stakeholders.

By communicating and disseminating the project’s tangible and intangible results and achievements through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, VIBES has been able to not only go beyond its ambitious Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) but most importantly to lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes.

Annex 1. Contact List of VIBES Stakeholders

VIBES		Contact list of VIBES stakeholders												
Group list	Sub-group list	No	Group (please select from drop down list)	Sub-group (please select from drop down list)	Contact name	Gender (M/F)	Contact email	Organisation (if applicable)	Website (if applicable)	Country	Nominated by VIBES consortium partner	Stakeholders Board Member (YES/NO/MAYBE)	Comments	FOLLOW UP
Industrial developers	Thermoset composite material developers													
Industrial converters, dismantlers & end-users	Composite recyclers													
Technology/ Innovation Experts	Aeronautical													
Impact multipliers	Naval													
Other (please specify in comments)	Construction													
	Energy													
	Waste management													
	Logistics													
	Transport													
	Academics and/or Researchers													
	Technology and/or Innovation consultants													
	Policy makers													
	Media/ journalists or bloggers													
	Other (please specify in comments)													

Annex 2. Declaration of Acceptance and Informed Consent Form

Declaration of Acceptance

(for individuals appointed as members of the VIBES Stakeholders Board in their individual capacity)

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the VIBES Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference.

I pledge that I will participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board in my individual capacity and as such I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium.

I certify that no conflict of interests exists that could be considered as prejudicial to my independence in acting as a member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the Stakeholders Board, unless the VIBES consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as member of the Stakeholders Board as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as member of the VIBES Stakeholders Board may be used by the VIBES consortium for reporting purposes or to align the products and technologies offered by VIBES with the needs of final users to ensure that they make the most out of its value propositions.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are

We are contacting you in the framework of VIBES, a project funded by the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

VIBES aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

A detailed description of the project and description of how VIBES handles personal data is available through the project’s web site www.vibesproject.eu.

Project:

VIBES – Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology, based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials.

Project Coordinator:

Organisation name: FUNDACION AITIIP

Address: Polígono Industrial Empresarium, Calle Romero N°12, 50720 Zaragoza, Spain

Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager:

Organisation name: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Address: 11 El. Venizelou str, 55133 Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece.

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	Project Coordinator	Pere Castell	pere.castell@aitiip.com
2	Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager	Eirini Efthymiadou	info@vibesproject.eu ; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

What we need from you

We need you to participate in the VIBES Stakeholders Board with a view to participate in project activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and provide your views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

To effectively carry out the activities of the Stakeholders Board, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number).

- Some basic demographics (gender, nationality).
- Your professional information (organisation, job position, field of expertise).
- Your education information.
- Your opinions on the subject matter(s) of relevant events.

Why we need your data & what we will do with them

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out activities related to the Stakeholders Board and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of your participation in such activities. We also need to record your data to keep track of the implementation of the activities. The project’s deliverables that will be derived by activities in which you participate will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you.

We will share your data with other project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project’s evaluation.
- EU agencies and other authorities for project’s auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project activities and also to inform you about the project’s progress (e.g. by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How you can withdraw your consent

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in the Stakeholders Board and its related activities, including demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, to provide my views and feedback to guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of VIBES.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding VIBES activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex 3. Stakeholders Board Terms of Reference

Introduction

You have been invited to take part in the **VIBES Stakeholders Board (SB)** because you were nominated by at least one of the VIBES consortium partners as a key stakeholder. The following Terms of Reference are aimed at helping you understand what this involves before you decide to participate. Please take the time to read this document carefully and ask for any clarifications you may require.

VIBES in a nutshell

VIBES is a 4-year Research and Innovation Action running from June 2021 to May 2025, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI-JU) under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

The VIBES project aims to develop and demonstrate an innovative and cost-efficient **green technology solution** to resolve the **end-of-life issues of thermoset composites**, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. To reach its purpose, VIBES will initially focus on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised **100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM)**. In addition, the project will design and develop biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to **place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market**. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/ cost ratio in 3 **high-demand industrial sectors**: aeronautical, construction and naval industries. Finally, a **greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology** to treat the smart VIBES composites will be developed and implemented at pilot level. As a result, the decomposed materials will be **recovered and valorised as new feedstocks** for the development of new products. The whole system will be defined, from the dismantling of the parts of the composite, to collecting and directing to the recycling plant, receiving, handling and sorting of the materials.

In this context, the Stakeholders Board (SB) of VIBES will consist of experts and representatives of various stakeholder groups in the whole value chain of VIBES, with activity in both local and European settings, who will be strategically involved in key stages of the project to contribute with their expertise and represent the views and interests of their stakeholder groups, in order to better guide decisions in the project and boost the VIBES concept and its implementation in real economy.

The VIBES project brings together a consortium of **13 partners across 7 different EU member states**. You can find more information about VIBES and the consortium by visiting www.vibesproject.eu.

Role and benefits

Role

The SB is set up and operate to share its knowledge and expertise with the consortium of the project in key implementation stages. The role of the SB in the context of the project may be summed up as follows:

- **Provide feedback and insights for the development process of VIBES innovations** such as the bio-based materials and the recycling technology, by participating in discussions and activities as prospective users of the developed materials and technology, to enhance their practical value and usability; as well as

- **Be actively involved in VIBES dissemination activities** to create a multiplier effect in spreading the word on the project’s value propositions, knowledge and impact as well as facilitating the market uptake of the project’s results.

To fulfil this role, it is foreseen that the SB, during the course of the project, will participate in VIBES demonstration workshops, roundtables and technological breakfasts, and will interact on ad-hoc basis if necessary:

- **Demonstration workshop:** it is expected that the SB will help articulate and lead the organisation of at least one demonstration workshop, addressed to industry and other VIBES stakeholders, in order to get the necessary feedback and engagement in the technology and the soundness of the VIBES concept.
- **Roundtables:** it is expected that the SB will participate in at least two roundtables, to be organised at key turning points of the VIBES project, in order to open debate, share different perspectives and get feedback to boost the VIBES concept and its implementation.
- **Technological breakfast:** it is expected that specific members of the SB will participate in at least one technological breakfast for industrial professionals, to be organised as part of the VIBES training programme, in order to share their views and experience in the fields addressed by the VIBES project.
- **Ad-hoc interactions:** if deemed necessary, the support of the SB (either in its entirety or of specific members based on their particular expertise) will be requested for ad hoc needs.

Benefits

The project provides **several benefits to its SB members**, such as:

- **Networking opportunities and visibility** as an expert stakeholder in a large multi-stakeholder community in the VIBES domain.
- **First access to meaningful insights, knowledge and results** generated exclusively within the context of the project and its activities.
- Unique opportunity to **align the VIBES bio-based materials and recycling technology with the needs of their stakeholders** to ensure that they make the most out of their value propositions.

Terms of membership and Management

Terms of membership

The SB shall be composed of eminent experts coming from diverse backgrounds to offer a blend of expertise that represents various groups of stakeholders from the VIBES whole value chain (such as industrial developers and users, academics and researchers, technology and innovation consultants, policy makers, media representatives etc.) and experts involved in projects and initiatives that are relevant to VIBES. These experts will provide VIBES with valuable feedback aimed at aligning the project’s outcomes with the needs of users and stakeholders. Along these lines, at least 10 members of the Stakeholders Board (SB) will be initially selected with the possibility to further expand the SB in the future in order to draw from additional expertise and increase the outreach of VIBES. New members could be appointed to the SB when necessary and as the project evolves.

Although members of the SB may be selected because of their affiliations with key organisations, they serve on the SB in their **individual capacity** to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder

communities. **Members of the SB may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them** or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the VIBES consortium. Members of the SB are appointed for the entire duration of the project (48 months, from 1 June 2021 to 31 May 2025). If due to job changes or attrition, an SB member loses links to important networks or constituencies, the consortium may decide to fill in this gap by appointing additional members.

The contribution of SB members is on a **pro bono basis**, apart from the cases in which physical travel is involved and a specific budget for their reimbursement is foreseen in the framework of the project. In such cases, the travel and accommodation expenses of SB members will be reimbursed by the project. Moreover, participation in the SB is **entirely voluntary**. There will be no adverse consequences if an SB member decides not to participate or to withdraw at any stage. In fact, SB members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager (see next section). They may also request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because this information cannot be traced back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Management

The SB is managed by the **Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that facilitates the communications and interactions between the SB and the consortium, ensuring that SB members are not overloaded. The Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager will also ensure that for each task requiring input from the SB, the partners have beforehand prepared an action plan and all necessary briefings and material. Only then, will the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager introduce a partner who may directly communicate with the SB in order to achieve the expected goals at each time.

Contact point

Any enquiry, complaint or concern about any aspect of your experience as a member of the Stakeholders Board (SB) can be addressed to the **VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager** that oversees the set up and manages the SB. The contact details of the Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager are provided below:

VIBES Communication, Training and Stakeholders Manager: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS P.C.

Contact person: Eirini Efthymiadou

Phone: +30 2310 411 191

Email: info@vibesproject.eu; efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr

Project website: www.vibesproject.eu

Annex 4. Document and Presentation Templates

VIBES

Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite
Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology
based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement 101023190

DX.Y “Title of Deliverable”

Work Package X

Responsible Partner: Name of Partner

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu

VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

VIBES has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

 VIBES Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

www.vibesproject.eu

IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

Title

Location

Date

Name

Email

Organisation

 BBiJU

 Bio-based Industries Consortium

 Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

 VIBES Green
Chemistry
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IMPROVING RECYCLABILITY OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS THROUGH A GREENER RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY BASED ON REVERSIBLE BIOBASED BONDING MATERIALS

Title

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This project has received funding from the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023190. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Annex 5. VIBES Presence on Social Media

VIBES Page on Twitter/X

VIBES Project 2021- 2025

254 posts

VIBES Project 2021- 2025

@VIBESEU2

VIBES: an [#innovative](#) and [#cost-efficient](#) [#green](#) technology solution for [#thermoset composites](#)' end-of-life.
[@CBE_JU](#) [@EU_H2020](#) funded project.

[vibesproject.eu](#) Joined June 2021

1,056 Following 360 Followers

Posts Replies Highlights Articles Media Likes

Pinned post

VIBES Project 2021- 2025 @VIBESEU2 · May 12 Promote

VIBES Final Event: Sustainable Composites Innovation

On 8th May 2025, the VIBES project celebrated 4 years of breakthroughs in recyclable thermoset composites at its final event in Barcelona. Experts shared insights on advancing the circular economy and overcoming [Show more](#)

VIBES Page and Metrics on LinkedIn

VIBES Project 2021-2025
 A green technology solution for thermoset composites' end-of-life.
 Biotechnology Research - 802 followers - 11-50 employees

Message Following

Home About **Posts** Jobs People

All Images Videos Articles Documents

Sort by: Top

VIBES Project 2021-2025
 802 followers
 23h •

Explore the last issue of the VIBES newsletter, celebrating our achievements in recyclable thermoset composites and the future of sustainable materials. From cutting-edge innovations to real-world impact, discover what we've accomplished! ...more

VIBES Project Newsletter

VIBES Project: The Journey Comes Full Circle
 VIBES Project 2021-2025

Maurice N Collins and 9 others 1 comment - 1 repost

NEWSLETTER

VIBES Value-Based Innovation for Business and Society

VIBES Project Newsletter

Welcome to the VIBES Newsletter

By VIBES Project 2021-2025
802 followers

Published monthly
335 subscribers

[Edit](#) [Share](#)

7 editions [Create new edition](#)

Get up to 10x more impressions by boosting this article [Boost](#)

Published 23 hours ago

VIBES Project: The Journey Comes Full Circle

VIBES Project 2021-2025

[Maurice N Collins and 9 others](#) 1 comment

Follower highlights ?

802
Total followers

184
New followers in the last 365 days

Follower demographics ?

Industry ▾

Highlights

Data for 5/13/2024 - 5/12/2025

69,493
Impressions

1,026
Reactions

17
Comments

22
Reposts

Metrics

Impressions ▾

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Organic	39,210
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Sponsored	30,283

VIBES Page and Metrics on Facebook

Views 2.5K
 Reach 1.8K ↑ 100%
 3-second views 164 ↑ 221.6%
 1-minute views 0 ↓ 100%
 Content interactions 665 ↑ 100%
 Watch time 41m 1s ↑ 162.2%

Reach breakdown

1 Apr 2023 - 16 Apr 2025

Total
1,768 ↑ 100%

From followers
153

From non-followers
1,639

VIBES Page on YouTube

VIBES Project

@vibesproject2291 · 18 subscribers · 5 videos

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solu...[more](#)

vibesproject.eu

Customize channel

Manage videos

Home Videos Playlists Posts

Videos

<p>VIBES Project 2021-2025 332 views · 3 years ago</p>				
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Annex 6. VIBES Seventh Newsletter

Welcome to the seventh issue of the VIBES newsletter

Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology.

Highlighting Project Achievements

VIBES highlights a series of significant recent advancements that reflect its commitment to sustainability, innovation, and real-world impact. Key collaborative work of the VIBES consortium in research and development (R&D) have led to the creation of novel materials and green technologies that showcase promising solutions in the field of recyclable thermoset composites.

The project has successfully developed bisphenol-free epoxy resins derived from biobased materials. Some of these resins incorporate Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM), which enhance the reusability and revalorisation of thermoset epoxy-based composites. Additionally, lignin-derived carbon fibres and flax fabrics have been introduced as sustainable alternatives for reinforcing thermoset composites. Notably, the VIBES team has pioneered a green recycling technology for thermoset epoxy-based composites, offering an innovative solution that revolutionises the revalorisation process and introduces a more sustainable chemical approach to debonding thermoset composites.

On the application side, the project has achieved impressive real-world demonstrations. Thermoset composite panels made with the new bisphenol-free epoxy resins have been produced and tested for both the naval and construction industries. A key milestone was the production of the first thermoset composite panel for the construction sector, made with the new bisphenol-free epoxy resin. This panel, featuring glass fibre reinforcement, was specifically designed to meet the rigorous demands of the infusion process and various construction applications. In the naval sector, the produced thermoset composite panel with flax reinforcement showed promising performance, meeting and, in certain aspects, exceeding anticipated industry requirements. Additionally, in aeronautics, a recyclable flax-reinforced composite was successfully tested for non-structural components, further advancing sustainable practices in the sector.

Furthermore, a pilot plant dedicated to recycling thermoset composites has been designed. Using eco-friendly processes, this plant holds great potential for separating and revalorising thermoset composites from industries such as construction, naval, and aeronautics.

For more details on VIBES exciting developments, the project's second promotional leaflet is available [here](#). You can also visit the [news section](#) of the VIBES website for more detailed updates on recent project developments.

Celebrating Fruitful Collaboration

On November 13, 2024, the VIBES consortium partners gathered together in Zaragoza, Spain, hosted by project coordinator AITIIP, to mark 42 months of progress. The meeting provided an opportunity to reflect on project achievements, discuss plans for the upcoming semester, and explore future developments. While most partners were able to engage in person and forge valuable connections, some consortium members participated remotely.

Throughout the meeting, key partners were filmed sharing brief statements about their roles and accomplishments within the project. These statements will be featured in an upcoming promotional video to be released in the coming months.

To conclude the meeting, consortium members had the opportunity to tour the AITIIP facilities, guided by the welcoming AITIIP team involved in the VIBES project.

Engaging with Stakeholders

The day after the VIBES consortium meeting, the second roundtable meeting took place in Zaragoza on November 14, 2024, hosted by AITTIP. This event brought together a panel of stakeholders and project partners to discuss project successes and explore strategies for the path ahead.

Key presentations included advancements in sustainable thermoset composites, upscaling components, and innovative recycling technologies. Special attention was given to recyclable thermoset composites and their technical validation across industries like aeronautics, construction, and naval sectors. The roundtable discussion focused on biobased materials for thermoset composites and debonding technologies, aligning with EU bioeconomy and circular economy policies.

The roundtable facilitated valuable insights for future R&D collaborations and pilot implementations, highlighting the consortium's commitment to driving sustainable innovation and fostering impactful partnerships.

For more information, visit the [news section](#) of the VIBES website.

What's Next?

In the final six months of the project, efforts will focus on the following key activities:

- Completing the thermoset composites recycling pilot plant.
- Finalising the sustainable chemical debonding process and the valorisation of recycled components.
- Concluding sustainability studies on the developed solutions.
- Further developing innovation and business plans to support the exploitation of key project outcomes.
- Continuing communication, dissemination, and training efforts to promote project results and facilitate knowledge transfer.

VIBES

Recycling Plant

[Visit the project's website](#)

Annex 7. VIBES Eighth Newsletter and Feedback Questionnaire

Newsletter issue #8

13 May 2025

Welcome to the eighth and final issue of the **VIBES newsletter**

Paving the Way for Sustainable Thermoset Composites

The Journey Comes Full Circle

After four years of research, innovation, and collaboration, the **VIBES project** has successfully concluded its mission: to enhance the recyclability of thermoset composite materials through **biobased components** and a **greener chemical recycling process**.

From cutting-edge material development to real-world demonstrations in **construction, aeronautics, and naval sectors**, VIBES has delivered tangible results that push the boundaries of what's possible in sustainable composites.

This **final issue** wraps up our key achievements and highlights from our final conference and workshop.

Highlights from the Final Conference & Workshop

The VIBES project has officially concluded with a successful **Final Conference** and **Workshop** held on **8th May 2025** in Barcelona. Organised in a hybrid format, the event marked a key milestone in the project's four-year journey of advancing the recyclability of thermoset composites through biobased materials and eco-friendly chemical recycling.

The event brought together experts, researchers, and industry stakeholders to discuss:

- VIBES innovations: **biobased epoxy resins, biobased fibre reinforcements, and an eco-friendly thermoset composites recycling solution.**
- Regulatory insights into sustainable materials adoption.
- Real-world impact across key industrial sectors.
- A thought-provoking panel on **industrial adoption and EPR.**
- Engaging discussions on scaling up green technologies in **aeronautics, construction, and marine industries.**

 [Read More About the Event.](#)

What We've Achieved

Over the course of the project, VIBES has:

- Developed recyclable thermoset composites with **intrinsic recycling functionalities**
- Created new **biobased resins** and **natural fibre reinforcements**
- Designed a **pilot plant** to demonstrate **eco-friendly chemical recycling**
- Delivered training workshops, summer schools, and dissemination to build capacity across Europe

We have prepared an **exclusive video** featuring VIBES team members as they share their experiences, challenges, and the impact of their work.

Watch the video: <https://vibesproject.eu/promotional-material/>

Explore the project's [Layman's Report](#) for more.

Tell Us What You Think – Final Feedback Request

Have you enjoyed reading the **VIBES newsletters**?
 What worked for you, and what could be improved?

Please take a moment to share your thoughts and help us improve future science communication efforts:

[Give Your Feedback on Our Newsletters](#)

Your voice matters!

What's Next?

Although the project has officially ended, the impact continues:

- VIBES technologies will move toward licensing, consulting, and further R&D.
- Partners will keep training and engaging new stakeholders.
- The vision for circular thermoset composites lives on.

Explore our [Scientific Publications](#) to access the knowledge we've shared with the global community.

Thank you for being part of the VIBES journey.

Together, we've made a lasting impact on sustainable materials.

VIBES Project Newsletter Feedback

We appreciate your time and interest in the VIBES project! Your feedback helps us understand the impact of our communication and improve future dissemination efforts.

** Indicates required question*

1. Which of the following best describes your role or stakeholder group? *

Mark only one oval.

- Research / Academia
- Technology / Innovation
- Industry
- Policy Maker / Public Authority
- Media / Communication
- Citizen / General Public
- Other: _____

2. Have you read any of VIBES e-newsletter editions? (select all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- VIBES LinkedIn newsletter editions
- VIBES Mailchimp newsletter editions
- Not sure / I didn't read the newsletters

Awareness and Impact

3. Did the VIBES e-newsletters increase your awareness or understanding of any of *
the following? (select all that apply)

Check all that apply.

- The environmental impact of thermoset composites
- Circular economy solutions for composites
- Biobased composite components
- Green recycling technologies
- Policy relevance and EU climate goals
- Other: _____

4. Which content elements were most valuable to you across the e-newsletters? *
(select all that apply)

Check all that apply.

- Project progress and updates
- Key achievements and results
- Practical applications in industry
- Policy and market insights
- Recommendations for stakeholders
- Visuals and infographics
- Other: _____

5. Did the VIBES e-newsletters inspire or support any of the following actions? *
(select all that apply)

Check all that apply.

- I shared it with colleagues or networks
- I followed up on a topic mentioned (e.g. visited project website, read a news article)
- It supported my research or policy work
- It led to ideas for implementation or collaboration
- Not yet, but I plan to
- None of the above
- Other: _____

Overall Evaluation and Future Interests

6. Overall, how would you rate your overall satisfaction with the VIBES e-newsletter *
editions?

Mark only one oval.

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very dissatisfied

7. How do you prefer to receive updates on EU-funded projects like VIBES? *

Mark only one oval.

- E-newsletters
- Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter/X)
- Project website
- Webinars or events
- Other: _____

8. Do you have suggestions for improvement or topics you would like to see covered in similar projects?

ANNEX 8. VIBES Eighth Press Release

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu
VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

PRESS RELEASE

17/12/2024

VIBES Project: Pioneering Sustainable Innovations in Thermoset Composites

The VIBES project has made substantial progress, highlighting its commitment to sustainability, innovation, and industry advancement. Among its key achievements are the development of bisphenol-free epoxy resins derived from biobased materials, enhanced with Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM) to improve recyclability, and the introduction of lignin-derived carbon fibres and flax fabrics as sustainable reinforcements for thermoset composites. Additionally, the project has pioneered a green recycling technology for thermoset composites, offering an eco-friendly chemical debonding solution.

These innovations have been successfully demonstrated across various industries. In construction, thermoset composite panels with glass and flax reinforcements were produced for diverse applications. In the naval sector, flax-reinforced panels performed well, meeting and, in certain aspects, surpassing expected standards. For aeronautics, recyclable flax-reinforced composites were validated for non-structural components.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU), now known as Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), under European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 101023190). The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Another significant milestone is the design of a cutting-edge recycling pilot plant, employing eco-friendly methods to revalorise thermoset composites from construction, naval, and aeronautics industries.

On November 13, 2024, the VIBES consortium gathered in Zaragoza, Spain, hosted by AITIIP, to review progress and plan for the project's final phase. Partner contributions captured during the meeting will be featured in an upcoming promotional video. A stakeholder roundtable held the next day provided valuable discussions on sustainable composites, innovative recycling, and alignment with EU circular economy policies, paving the way for future collaborations.

In its final phase, the project will focus on completing the recycling pilot plant, finalising the chemical debonding process and valorisation of components, concluding sustainability assessments, advancing innovation and business strategies, and enhancing communication, dissemination, and training initiatives.

Stay informed about the latest developments and updates from the VIBES project by visiting the official website at www.vibesproject.eu. Don't forget to subscribe to our newsletter and follow VIBES on social media to stay connected.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU), now known as Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 101023190). The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

ANNEX 9. VIBES Ninth Press Release

CONTACT US: info@vibesproject.eu
VISIT: www.vibesproject.eu

PRESS RELEASE

13/05/2025

The VIBES Project Officially Concludes After Four Years of Groundbreaking Research and Innovation in Circular Composites

The VIBES project, a pioneering initiative aimed at enhancing the recyclability of thermoset composite materials, has officially concluded after four years of transformative research and innovation. The project, funded by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE-JU) under Horizon 2020, brought together partners from across Europe to achieve major milestones in the development of sustainable, biobased solutions for thermoset composite materials.

The successful completion of the project was marked by a Final Conference and Workshop held in Barcelona on 8th May 2025. The hybrid event brought together experts, stakeholders, and industry leaders to celebrate the achievements of the VIBES project and discuss its long-term impact on the future of circular composites.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU), now known as Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 101023190). The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Key Achievements of the VIBES Project Include:

- **Development of Biobased Epoxy Resins and Natural Fibre Reinforcements:** New, sustainable alternatives that replace traditional petrochemical-based materials, offering enhanced recyclability and environmental benefits.
- **Design of Recyclable Thermoset Composites:** Innovations in composite material design that allow for easier recycling, reducing waste and supporting a circular economy.
- **Deployment of a Pilot Plant for Eco-friendly Recycling:** A cutting-edge pilot plant that demonstrated the viability of eco-friendly chemical recycling technologies for thermoset composites, showcasing a scalable solution for material recovery.

Throughout its lifetime, the VIBES project engaged stakeholders, delivered training, and produced scientific publications that have advanced the field of circular composites. With its results, VIBES has made significant contributions to reducing plastic waste, enabling material recovery, and supporting sustainable product development across industries such as construction, aeronautics, and naval engineering.

Highlights of VIBES' Impact:

- **Training and Knowledge Sharing:** The project delivered numerous training workshops, summer schools, and targeted dissemination activities to foster knowledge transfer and promote the uptake of recyclable composites across sectors.
- **Scientific Contributions:** VIBES produced valuable scientific publications and a Layman's Report, ensuring that the knowledge generated throughout the project is widely accessible and can inspire further innovation in the field.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The project engaged stakeholders through roundtables, industry events, and online resources, building a collaborative network to drive forward the transition to circular composites.

VIBES has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU), now known as Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 101023190). The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

While the project has officially concluded, the work continues. Project partners are committed to advancing the technologies developed through VIBES, with plans for licensing, consulting, and further R&D to ensure real-world deployment and commercialisation. Training activities will also continue, supporting the wider adoption of recyclable composites in various industries.

For more information, please visit the VIBES project website at www.vibesproject.eu.

Disclaimer

This press release reflects solely the author's view, and the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (JU), now known as Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU), is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Annex 10. Communication and Dissemination Reporting Template

The form below has been designed to help keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activities of the project. As a reminder, communication and dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, conferences, fairs, forums, workshops, roundtables, press releases, newsletters, publications, presentations etc. Please, complete ANY RELEVANT PARTS of the form below each time you perform a communication or dissemination activity, either small or large.																
Partner name																
No.	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity	Title of publication (journal, newspaper etc.) or event (conference, workshop, training, roundtable, info-day, exhibition, TV programme etc.)	Title of article (scientific, press release, news etc.) or presentation given by the partner	Type of audience	Size of audience (inc. of persons per type of audience)	Language used/ countries reached out	Role and description of partner organisation's involvement (e.g. facilitator)	Type of project promotional material used (e.g. leaflets, infographic, poster or infographic roll-ups etc.)	Quantity of project promotional material handed out (inc. of copies distributed per type of material)	Name of other VIBES partners or external organisations responsible / involved	Short description of the activity	Evidence: URL, screenshot, photo (given that the target group has given its consent)	Significant contacts made (name, position, organisation; if consent, to store and share email address, telephone)	Other comments
1																
2																
3																

Annex 11. News Reporting Template

News about Project Developments

Picture (if available)	
Title	
News (main content)	
Key words/ hashtags (for social media)	

Attachments

Please attach any relevant pictures/ images as separate jpg files with as high resolution as possible.

Annex 12. Event Reporting Form

Event's Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organisers	
Audience (number and type, including % of female attendees)	
Duration	

Event's goals, objectives and relevance to VIBES

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g. to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). Was the event relevant to VIBES? To what extent?

Organisation of the event

This section is completed only in case of organising a project event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organised?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Promotional activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the VIBES project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observation that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

Annexes: Attachments

If applicable, the following Annexes should be attached:

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if applicable)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g. leaflets, infographic, newsletters etc.)

Annex 13. External Conferences and Events Template

		Identified External Conferences and Events							
No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Date	Location	Registration fees	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission etc)	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Added by (Partner)
1									
2									
3									